

**INFLUENCE OF DESIGN LIFE IN A CRITICAL
OFFSHORE STRUCTURAL CONNECTION DUE TO THE
INHERENT GAP AT MATING SURFACES - A STUDY BY
FEA APPROACH**

A Thesis

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for Award of
POST DOCTORAL FELLOW

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DECLARATION

I hereby declare that except where specific reference is made to the work of others, the contents of this thesis are original and have not been submitted in whole or in part for consideration for any other degree or qualification in this, or any other university. This thesis is my own work and does not contain any outcome of work done in collaboration with others, except as specified in the text and Acknowledgements.

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SYNOPSIS

INFLUENCE ON DESIGN LIFE IN A CRITICAL OFFSHORE STRUCTURAL CONNECTION DUE TO THE INHERENT GAP AT MATING SURFACES – A STUDY BY FEA APPROACH

INTRODUCTION

While fabrication of certain offshore structural cutter ladder components, a situation can arise where the gap may be formed due to assembly level exceeding tolerance limit, improper heat or process control during fabrication. This gap will lead to reduce the pretension force and design life of bolt as well as mating part hence fatigue failure will happen in the connection due to lack of slip resistance on the joint. The slip resistance and design life can be improved by adding shims on the connection if gaps are present in the connection.

In this research work is mainly focusing on the assembly level gap on cutter ladder lower part and upper part assembly connection, this gap may lead to inadequate design life failure in dynamic load applied on that.

There are two loading conditions considered in the cutter ladder joints,

1. Floating condition
2. Operational condition

Floating Condition: In this condition the machine is in floating stage and the cutter ladder will be stayed by stay wire which is connected on the structure called “A” frame. In this condition self-weight only acts on the connection no other dynamic load acts on that part.

The floating condition are mentioned in Figure 1 and Figure 2.

Figure 1: Floating condition

Figure 2: General Assembly in floating condition

Operational condition: In this condition the machine is under operation mode, the following forces will be applied on the connection.

1. Cutter cutting force
2. Cutter ladder lifting force
3. Anchoring force on both side
4. Hydro dynamic load.
5. Pipe line suction force

The operational condition and its loading patterns are mentioned in Figure 3 to Figure 5.

Figure 3: Operation condition

Figure 4: Detailed view on research Area

Figure 4: Loading pattern

In this research work, the effect of assembly level gap and shimming process on design life is focused. Finite element analysis methods are used to derive the Von Mises stress, membrane stress and fatigue damage life. Alternative or retrofit solution will be provided after the research work. This type of assembly level gap is possible in all heavy fabrication industry, the result of this research work will provide better solution which will be useful for all assembly level gap connection.

This study summarizes the FE-analyses and damage life calculation results for the cutter ladder flanged connection to evaluate the possible inside gaps.

It has to be performed for ultimate limit state and fatigue calculation for an adapt model with maximum inside gap (outside closed) to the maximum permissible of 2% inclination.

Model characteristics:

- 3D model FE Analysis
- Linear elastic and plastic S355 material behavior
- Quasi- static mechanical load,

- Consideration of “large strain” option,
- Consideration of contact between modelled parts,
- Bonded contact conditions between bolt/washer – flange connection,
- Investigation for the max. Permissible flange inside gap of 2%.
- The FE- analysis on Cutter ladder flanged connection.
- The FE model with a part of the pipe shells and the flanges in fine meshes.
- The pre-stressed bolts are modelled with 3D or 2D bolt 2D elements.
- The flanges sides are with bonded contact conditions for the contact of washer.
- In the ultimate limit state results to recognize whether the gap will be closed after bolt pretension or not.
- FAT 36 considered on weld seam and bolted connection.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Definition of Fatigue: A standard definition of the term fatigue, as it applies to metals, from EN1993 – 9 and EN 1090-2 the process of initiation and propagation of cracks through a structural part due to action of fluctuating stress. That means the process of progressive localized permanent structural change occurring in a material subjected to conditions that produce fluctuating stresses and strains at some point or points and that may culminate in cracks or complete fracture after a sufficient number of fluctuations. A more straight forward definition for fatigue is the nucleation of cracks in a structure resulting from cyclic loading.

Void Slip planes or resistance are inherent in the material join together to form these cracks. The three chronological stages a fatigue crack undergoes are

1. Crack initiation
2. Crack Propagation
3. Structural Fracture

The fatigue strength of a material differs from the static strength in that the static strength is related to a single applied load while the fatigue strength is dependent upon repeated loading that varies over time. Classical fatigue theory is typically considered valid for metals only.

A Historical Perspective of Fatigue: The first study of fatigue, relating to a structural change in metals due to repeated loading, dates back to 1838 when Wilhelm Albert conducted research on hoisting chains used in mining. Jean-Victor Poncelet, a French engineer and mathematician, coined the term *fatigue* to describe the wearing down of a material due to changes in loading in 1839 during lectures at a military school in Metz, France. The first in-depth fatigue analysis involving testing and the development of S-N curves is credited to August Wöhler in 1860 for a study of failures of railroad axles.

Much of this early fatigue-related research was conducted to analyze metallic machinery that was used extensively during the Industrial Revolution of the 19th century. A large amount of new information has been generated and many original analysis methods have been developed relating to fatigue subsequent to these early studies. Research on fatigue in offshore structures are important because of the typical loading and unloading conditions has played a critical role in the development of the science of metal fatigue.

Many fatigue failures and disasters in aero structures have been recorded. The in-flight disintegration of a Comet I airplane in 1954 after a long service history is one of the first notable failure events in aerospace that was attributed to fatigue. The particular airplane that failed was actually the first passenger plane with a jet engine to go in to active service. Just a few weeks after the first Comet I event, another Comet I disintegrated inflight. All service of the aircraft was then immediately suspended. Subsequent testing, as detailed in the Federal Aviation Administration Damage

Tolerance Assessment, revealed that the cause of the disasters was a fatigue failure originating at the cabin windows.

Stress-Life Approach: There are different methods commonly used to conduct fatigue analysis of metals. Stress-Life, Strain-Life, and some applications of Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics (LEFM) can all be employed when attempting to predict the nucleation of cracks in metals. The Stress-Life or S-N approach is the most frequently used and well established method of fatigue life prediction.

Variable Amplitude Loading: Fatigue loading is generally represented as a spectrum, which is a series of maximum and minimum cycles of loading that are grouped together. These loading cycles have varying stress amplitudes. This is true especially this cutter ladder structure that are often subjected to complex load patterns.

Definition of a Stress Concentration: States that a stress concentration, also sometimes referred to as a stress raiser is defined as a local stress increase in the intensity of a stress field due to discontinuity. Stress concentrations are means stress concentration factors, typically denoted by the symbol K_t , the stress concentration factor, or SCF, is defined as the ratio of the highest stress to a reference stress calculable from simple theory.

Use of Stress Concentrations in Fatigue Analysis: Stress concentration factors play a critical role in any detailed metal fatigue analysis. Within a structure, fatigue cracks are most likely to nucleate in the region where the stress at its peak. The highest stresses in a body will occur at geometric features including holes, radii, notches, gap etc. These peak stresses are calculated from stress concentration factors. Therefore it is essential that accurately determined SCFs are used to ensure that a proper fatigue life prediction of any structure has been performed. The use of stress concentration factors in cutter ladder structure is particularly important due to the high number of stress raising features that exist in offshore platform component design, in particular fastener holes and gaps.

Overview of Previous Research on assembly level gap on structural connections

There have been numerous studies of situations involving the assembly level gap on structural connection due to the proximity of various geometric features with respect to certain applied loading conditions. Some of these studies are simplistic while others are very complex, involving extensive testing and the use of finite element models to predict stress values at critical locations. The majority of previous research on the phenomenon of stress concentration factors interactions is based on a detailed study of a specific situation or situations involving closely spaced features subjected to a particular loading profile. Also, many of the earlier studies on this specific topic are related to lattice and tubular tower structures. These instances seem to arise or occur in this field more frequently than in any other engineering discipline.

RATIONALE OF THE STUDY

This section outlines the purposes and goals for the research contained in this paper that relates to interacting assembly level gap on connections. The two main reasons for this study relating to stress concentration factor and design life for geometric features placed in close proximity share equal importance. Specific details are provided relating to both an academic justification as well as an industry justification for this research. It is generally hoped that the information contained in this dissertation can be used by students, academic professionals and industry professionals alike to both provide a reference for specific situations of stress concentration factor interactions and to present K_t values that engineers and analysts can use as part of a detailed fatigue and or stress analysis for this offshore structures.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

This research study focuses on the development of stress concentration factors modification and fatigue damage life for geometric features placed in close proximity with respect to one another. K_t modification factors are commonly applied to account for various conditions that affect the fatigue performance of critical details. Some examples of these conditions include assembly level gap on connection, countersunk holes,

inadequate geometry level tolerance, blending, dents, burrs, cold working and flapper peening. The applied mod factors may be either helpful or detrimental to fatigue life.

The assembly level gap developed through this research were determined through finite element modeling and analysis.

- The 3D modelling will be done through ANSYS spaceclaim
- Meshing and boundary condition will be done through ANSYS Prepost.
- Analysis will be carried out through ANSYS Solver.

The research concludes with a general summary of the results. The result values obtained by finite element analysis from the assembly level gap connection are compared with the determined finite element analysis of perfect standard connection result.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study consists of an in-depth analysis of various instances that occur in-situ repair, retrofit solution related to the assembly level gap critical connection in offshore structure, onshore structure, lattice tower structural connection, tubular tower flanged connection and heavy fabrication industry during the fabrication or assembly process.

The goal is to provide original result with perfect connection and the result with assembly level gap connection with respect to these specific connections in Heavy Fabrication Industries.

Various thickness shims are introduced in the assembly level gap connection to derive the improved design life.

Comprehensive summaries of the closed gap joint FE Analysis as well assembly level gap FE Analysis are conducted as part of this research project will also be presented in the thesis.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Purpose

Stress and strain concentrations in assembly level gap in offshore critical structural connections are problematic because it leads to strength deteriorations, damage accumulations and eventually to failure. This paper seeks to establish how the assembly gaps get affected by stresses and strains, and the need to shim these assembly gaps.

The influence of the assembly gap and shims on the strains and stresses of a bolted offshore structure has to be carried out using a three-dimensionally nonlinear static analysis using the finite element software ANSYS.

The trend to check the elastic and allowable plastic strain behaviors depicted by the assembled structure with gap and without gap as well the shimming procedure in the offshore structural industry.

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ABSTRACT

During fabrication of certain offshore structural cutter ladder components, a situation can arise where the gap may formed due to assembly level exceeded tolerance limit, improper heat or process control during fabrication. This gap will lead to reduce the pretension force and design life of bolt as well matting part hence fatigue failure will happen in the connection due to lack of slip resistance on the joint and this will provide stress concentration on the mating structural member. The slip resistance and design life can be improved by adding shims on the connection is gaps are presented in the connection. In this dissertation, the combined effect of stress concentrations and pretension losses are placed in close proximity to each other and their impact on fatigue performance is studied, the fatigue S-N data taken from Recommendations for Fatigue Design of Welded Joints and Components – IIW collection

This research work is mainly focusing on the assembly level gap on offshore cutter ladder lower part and upper part assembly connection; this gap may lead to inadequate design life failure in dynamic load applied on that.

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Cutter Suction Dredger

The cutter suction Dredger will be a non-propelled cutter suction dredger suitable for dredging operations in protected (inland) waters. The pontoon will be constructed of steel.

The general layout will be such that the pontoon can carry the complete dredging installation with other necessary equipment and 50 tons of stores, fuel and fresh water at a maximum draught of 1.5 m.

1.1.1 The main installations

Cutter ladder with cutter and cutter drive

Ladder hoisting system with gantry and winch

Dredger swing system with two side winches

Suction and discharge installation with one dredge pump and drive.

Auxiliary engine(s) with auxiliaries

Hydraulic system with power unit

Spud system with spud carrier, two spuds and hoisting arrangements

The principal dimensions and characteristics are as follows: -

- Length of pontoon 25.0 m.
- Length overall with ladder raised 35.0 m
- Breadth moulded 8 m
- Depth at side 3 mt approx.
- Maximum draught (with 50 tons stores) 1.5 mtr
- Maximum dredging depth 10.0 m
- Inside diameter of suction pipe 450 mm
- Inside diameter of discharge line 400 mm
- Cutter drive (hydraulic) 150-200 HP

Watertight transverse and longitudinal bulkheads as well compartments will subdivide the pontoon, the elements of cutter ladder is shown in figure 1.1 and figure 1.2.

Figure: 1.1 Floating condition

Figure: 1.2 General Assembly in floating condition

1.1.2 Dredging equipment

For making the production swing the Dredger is to be equipped with two hydraulically driven side winches, mounted on the main deck forward of the operator's control cabin.

In addition, the cutter will be hydraulically driven (two slow running motors) through a watertight gearbox. The cutter ladder-hoisting winch will be identical to both side winches.

For production and delivery of spoil one high pressure sand pump with a mixture capacity of at least 3500 m³/h to dredge fine sand from 10 m water depth and deliver the spoil via 1000 m floating and fixed pipeline ashore to be installed.

The Dredger will also be capable to dredge with satisfactory production at a minimum depth of 1.0 meter. The diesel engine and hydraulic installations (winches + cutter drive) shall be remotely controlled from the operator's cabin, so that dredging operation can be controlled by a single person.

After disconnecting the floating/fixed discharge pipe line and mounting a jetting nozzle on board the mixture can be thrown on either side of the Dredger up to a distance of at least 80 m.

For positioning the Dredger is equipped with two tubular steel spuds in the aft ship, one spud acting as fixed positioning spud, the second spud mounted in a spud carrier, movable by a hydraulic cylinder to make steps in the forward direction of the Dredger.

1.1.3 Installation trials

Installation trials are to check all installations, systems equipment etc. and will be done as per manufacturers recommendation and to be carried out The Dredger with all installations, systems, equipment, dredging installations winches, crane, piping systems, hydraulic installations, spud system, electric/electronic installation, ventilation, measuring systems etc.

These trials to include an inclining test for determination of weight, draught, trim, center of gravity etc. and further (as far as possible) a complete series of tests for the dredging installation including capacity measurements of the dredge pump system (pumping river water) and Determination of the pressure and throwing distance for the jetting system.

The dredging trials is to demonstrate the designated output is achieved 500 Cu.m of solid / hour. Pre dredging and post dredging survey to assess quantity of dredged soil / output will be undertaken by IWAI. Dredging trials will be done within one month of provisional acceptance. Dredging trials to be done when dredging water. Approval from authorities for dredging soil to be arranged by the owner. Density and velocity of mixture may not be measured with available tools on board.

1.2 HULL STEELWORK

The pontoon including deckhouse, cutter ladder and spud carriage shall be constructed of steel throughout. The scantlings of all structural members shall comply with the Rules and Regulations of the Classification Society.

Good continuity of structural members in basic hull structure shall be maintained. Care shall be taken to obtain proper alignment of important structural members. Where members are discontinuous, the continuity shall be provided by means of suitable tapers, overlaps and/or brackets.

The Dredger shall have a single bottom construction and one continuous main deck. Openings in hull and deck, discontinuities in way of ladder well and spud carriage well, heavy loaded parts under ladder gantry, winches, spuds and discharge line shall be compensated and/or reinforced by plating of increased thickness.

1.2.1 Materials

“The steel to be used is to be of IS 2062 Grade B or equivalent and classification society shall carry out necessary testing of the samples of steel as required by class”

(b) Sub-heading – steel wire rope – The second sentence will be substituted ‘Tensile strength of the wires to be in accordance with requirement of class wires to be of suitable construction, depending on function.’”

1.2.2 Rolled steel

Hull materials and all other rolled steel, to be tested as per the rules of the Class, of which certificates have to be submitted. The steel must have good welding qualities and should have a carbon percentage not exceeding 0.2%.

Before the material is used in the construction, rust and mill scale must be removed by means of steel grit blasting according to approved Standard. Immediately after the steel grit blasting, one coat of approved shop primer with a thickness of approx. 20 micron to be applied as a temporary protection.

1.2.3 Cast steel

Steel castings shall be only from first-class approved foundry and of approved design. Quality and testing in accordance with the rules of the Class., Castings must be free from blowholes or other defects.

1.2.4 Brass/copper

Brass for fittings, sidelights etc. to be of two parts of copper and one, part of zinc.

Those parts which must have a high elastic limit, such as for bolts and pins for hinges, Delta metal or similar to be used. Copper pipes shall be according to Class requirements.

1.2.5 Bolts and nuts

All bolts and nuts to be of one approved standard. Throughout metric thread is to be used.

1.2.6 Steel wire rope

All steel wires to be of approved make, type and quality and to be delivered with the required certificates. Tensile strength of the wires to be in accordance with requirement of Class of suitable construction, depending on function. All wires are to be galvanized.

1.2.7 Preparation of materials.

When steel plates are deformed during transport, these are to be faired by rolling before use. Flanging of plates and brackets is generally not allowed. Plates and rolled sections to be cleaned and preserved.

Holes in steel construction for trunk passages and pipes or other passing, to be carried out in concert with the survey authority and the Class.

In way of watertight doors in bulkheads and in way of manholes, adequate additional stiffening to be provided.

All tanks, watertight bulkheads and other constructions to be pressure- or hose-tested after the work has been finished, in accordance with the requirements of the Class.

A tank-testing plan to be timely submitted for approval.

Before pressure-testing or hose-testing of any compartment or construction is carried out, it has to be offered for survey to the Class.

During the building, the correct line of the keel and the bottom sides are to be inspected regularly of determine any deformation of the hull, as a consequence of welding. Care should be taken that all parts of the hull remain accessible and where this is not possible, these places are to be coated with hot bitumastic and/or to be filled-up with cement.

1.2.8 Welding

All welding to be of excellent quality. During the welding operations all necessary precautions are to, be taken so that welds of high standards are obtained. All surfaces to be well cleaned and free from rust, paint etc. before welding is commenced.

Plate edges are to be flame-cut mechanically as much as possible. Where possible plates and sections to be interconnected by automatic welding methods. Where possible plates and sections to be interconnected by automatic welding methods.

Overhead welding to be avoided as far as possible and therefore necessary provisions to be taken for underhand welding where practical.

Manual, semi-automatic or automatic welding procedures and sequence for welding specific parts or respective steps in the process of assembling the structural blocks of the hull shall be selected in consultation with the surveyor of the Classification Society.

A complete welding list to be submitted for approval to the Class.

In this list particulars to be given, such as shape of welded joints, the manner of preliminary treatments, the dimensions of the weld and the type of electrodes to be used.

It is not allowed to perform welded connections with notches. Generally every part of the construction to be connected with continuous welds. Intermittent welding only to be performed with special permission of the Class. During the welding the relevant construction shall be dry.

Heavy parts of spuds and spud guides, cutter ladder gantry etc. to be preheated and annealed, accordance with the instructions of the Class

The welding to be performed with electrodes of approved make.

Welders, specially those who are working on the main connections, must be qualified and regularly tested.

A regular check of the quality of the welds by X-ray or similar methods to be carried out to the satisfaction of the class if considered necessary by the Class additional measures are to be taken

1.2.9 Quality of the welds

Welded decks, bulkheads, deckhouses and other constructions which are deformed by welding to be faired, in order to obtain fair work, complying with high standards. On the berth, the hull and sections to be earthed adequately.

Clamps, dogs and other means to bring material and equipment in the right position, to be removed in such a way that no visual marks and/or mechanical damage is left.

1.3 Cutter Installation

“Alternatively 150 – 200 hp for cutter drive with direct hydraulic drive is considered to be acceptable”

The specified power for cutter driver is varying. Cutter drive mentioned is gearbox and two hydraulic motor. Request to accept 150-170 hp with direct hydraulic drive.

The cutter installation to be designed for cutting loosely to medium packed sand with a cutting power of at least 200 HP.

The main objective is to achieve a large dredged area coverage per unit of time. The thickness of cutting will vary between about 0.2 m and 1.0 m with an average of about 0.70 m. Therefore relative large cutter dimensions in relation to the suction diameter to be chosen in combination with a high swing speed.

The dimensions, weight, ballast etc. of cutter ladder with cutter head and drive to be chosen in such a way that with ladder down the virtual weight in hoisting system will not be less than 180kN (cutter free from river bed).Alternatively 150-170HP for cutter drive with direct hydraulic drive is considered to be acceptable.

1.3.1 Ladder hoisting gantry – A Frame

“Alternatively Tubular steel construction for ladder hoisting gantry is acceptable”

The hoisting gantry on the fore ship to be an A-frame steel or tublar steel construction mounted via hinge constructions with an angle of about 60 degrees relative

to the main deck. The maximum height to be less than 5.50 m above water level for, the dredger in transport condition with 10 percent stores and zero water ballast. The arrangement is shown in figure 1.1.

Longitudinal stability and strength to be arranged by two diagonal steel pipes alongside the ladder well, with bolted or hinged connections on both ends. The operation conditions are shown in figure 1.3.

1.3.2 Cutter ladder

The top part of the cutter ladder to be an open box type steel construction with high stiffness and the lower part to be a steel pipe with a diameter of at least 1200 mm. The displacement of the ladder to be kept as small as possible.

Discontinuities in the steel constructions to be avoided and/or sufficient overlap to be chosen. In general edges of openings to be reinforced by strips or equivalent. The ladder to be hinged to the main pontoon at about 0.9 m below deck level by means of heavy trunnions.

For the hoisting system a number of sheaves to be mounted on the ladder. For the swing system two walking sheaves at top end of ladder, two guide rollers at halfway of the ladder and further two swiveling sheave blocks on the lower end of the ladder to be provided.

For the cutter drive and all other equipment etc. mounted in or on the ladder suitable foundations and local strengthening to be arranged. Means to be provided for fixing the ladder in up-position at deck level (hand operated heavy locking pins or equivalent).

Watertight parts in the ladder to be designed where sand deposits can be expected at inaccessible locations. These parts to be kept as small as possible, well preserved and filled with polyurethane foam or equivalent.

Figure 1.3 Operation condition

Figure 1.4 Detailed view on research Area

Figure 1.5 Loading pattern

1.3.3 Ladder hoisting winch

The ladder to be hoisted by a 4 parts hoisting arrangement and a hydraulic driven winch positioned directly in front of the operator's control cabin. This winch to be exactly identical to the side wire winches. The wire length to be suitable for a maximum dredging depth of 6 m with a minimum of 34 m wire on the drum. The highest position of ladder to be such that with one spud down, 10 percent stores and no water ballast cutter head repair or replacement operations can be carried out.

1.3.4 Side wire winches

Two side wire or swing winches to be installed on the main deck in front of the operator's control cabin. These winches to be driven by slow-running heavy duty radial piston hydraulic motors.

Further each winch to be provided with a hydraulic operated band-brake fitted on the winch drum. Braking of the releasing winch to be adjustable at some braking torque levels between 10 and 40 percent of nominal torque. Reversing of winches to be

effected by remote control from the operating desk. For securing the winches with hand-operated locking pins to be provided.

The capacities and drum dimensions are:

- drum diameter min. 520 mm
- drum length min. 500 mm
- drum wall thickness at least 32 mm
- drum capacity (max. 4 layers) at least 150 mm
- wire diameter 28 mm
- wire breaking strength 560 KN
- hauling pull on first layer (nominal) 130 KN
- ditto, peak-stalling (intermittent) 160 KN
- nominal continuous hauling speed 18 m/min.
- maximum intermittent hauling speed 24 m/min (reduced torque)
- maximum veering speed 35 m/min
- band-brake dynamic braking capacity 160 m/KV
- band-brake static braking capacity 200 KN

The length of each side wire to be at least 150 m.

1.3.5 Driving system

The cutter will be driven by two slow running hydraulic motors (identical type and size as side winches) via a gearbox, both mounted on the cutter ladder. The hydraulic motors to have a total rated output power of at least 200 HP at nominal speed, capable to deliver the nominal rated torque in a speed range from 40% to 100% of nominal speed. The gearbox to have a reduction such as necessary for a nominal cutter speed of 30 r.p.m. Alternatively 150- 200HP for cutter drive with direct hydraulic drive

is considered to be acceptable. The direction of rotation of the cutter to be clockwise seen from the motor, figure 1.4 and figure 1.5 shows the driving component in cutter ladder.

1.3.6 Coupling cutter drive

Between gearbox and cutter shaft a gear-type coupling with thrust plate based on the rated power and a machine factor of at least 2. The gear type coupling of approved make to be of the single type and to be provided with outboard water resistant rubber tightening sleeves.

1.3.7 Gearbox cutter drive

The gearbox to be specially designed for cutter driving , suitable for working below waterline level under all occurring angles and down to a water depth of about 6 m. The gearbox suitable for the required power.

The gearbox with built-in thrust bearing suitable for a continuous thrust of at least 15 tons.

The gearbox to be designed with a calculated average lifetime for the bearings of 40,000 hours and infinite lifetime for the gears (both for breaking and pitting, taking into account a machine factor of 2).

1.3.8 Cutter shaft and bearing

The cutter shaft to be designed for the required torque, possible overloads and further dynamic shock loads as can be expected under practical circumstances (large stones and/or local limestone areas).

1.4 Cutters

Two cutters with a diameter of about 1600 mm will have to be delivered and mounted, one cutter for handling light compact sand and one cutter for handling medium to heavy packed sand. Both cutters with identical hubs, buttress thread, inside ring diameter and distance ring base/hub. The inside ring diameter to be approx. 1400 mm. The light packed sand cutter the 5 blades and plain edges (crown type).

The medium packed sand cutter with serrated plain edges. Cutters suitable for the installed power, revs, ladder angles and suction mouth dimensions. Cutter material to be of high tensile manganese steel. Make of cutters, IHC, Esco or equivalent. Geometric design of cutters to be chosen in concert with OWNER.

1.4.1 Anchors, sheaves and guides

The mass of all four swing anchors to be 500 kgs each.

For each side wire two floating drums to be delivered Floating drums to keep swing wire will have negative result on anchor holding force.

In place of two floating drums, floaters may be considered Four swing anchors of Delta-type or equivalent; Four anchors with each a mass of 500 kgs to be supplied.

Fluke area and fluke angle shall be worked out for maximum holding power in loosely packed fine sand. The swiveling sheaves for side wires to be balanced and with suitable guiding plates for outgoing wire.

At the top of the ladder two walking sheaves and at about halfway of the cutter ladder two additional conical shaped rollers for guiding the side wires to be mounted.

Further for two 1500 kgs anchors separate short (hoisting) wires with floating balls complet with connections etc. to be delivered.

For each side wire two floaters to be delivered (keeping wire free from river bottom).

1.4.2 Suction and Discharge Installation

Discharge pipeline both floating pipeline 500 M and shore pipeline 500 M mentioned. If shore pipeline to be provided confirm whether it is steel pipeline.

The single pump installation is to be capable to discharge at a distance of 1000m. The bidder has to supply only floating discharge pipeline of total 500 m length.

The mixture capacities etc. and spoil density mentioned are varying in these clauses. For both i.e. discharging through pipeline and nozzle the pump capacity to be such that the mixture capacity is 2600 m³/hr. and spoil density is of 1.30 ton/m³.

The suction pipe line mounted at the underside of the ladder will deliver the spoil to the pump, driven by a diesel engine.

The dredge pump will be positioned as low as possible inside the pontoon and to be designed as a high pressure sand pump. The mixture or spoil capacity to be at least 2600cu m/h in case of a specific density of 1.3 ton/m³, assuming a discharge distance of about 1000 m.

This single pump installation will be able to deliver the spoil ashore through a 500 m floating pipe line and a 500 m fixed pipe line with a diameter 450 mm. After disconnecting these pipelines, the installation will also be able to deliver the mixture through a jetting nozzle system at a (throwing) distance of at least 80 m aside the dredger with a mixture capacity of at least 2500 m³/h and a specific density of 1.2 t/m³. The required pump pressures to be calculated by the Contractor and submitted to the OWNER for approval.

The total pumping distance is 1000 Mtrs. But shipyard to supply only 500 Mtrs. of floating discharge pipeline for each dredger.

1.4.3 Dredge pump

The single walled centrifugal as a high pressure sand pump mentioned in par. 6.5.1. The pump and 5- blade impeller to be designed for high efficiency, a pressure of at least 65 mwc at a nominal speed of about 450-500 revs. The pump to be able to realize a vacuum of about - 6 mwc (an absolute pressure of 0.4 bar) at nominal speed and without significant cavitation.

The pump casing to be a single piece steel casting with a wall thickness for unprotected areas of at least 75mm. Suction cover and shaft cover to be provided with wearing plates.

The impeller with a diameter of about 1.25 m to be of cast steel with an average blade thickness of at least 40 mm and fitted to the shaft by a thread connection.

One additional impeller with a smaller diameter to be delivered suitable to deliver a maximum quantity of spoil at nominal speed in case of a discharge distance of about 500 m and a spoil density of 1.3 t/m³.

The required pressure for this condition will be significantly less than 65 mwc (approx. 40-45 mwc) and has to be calculated by the Contractor.

Design and calculations of capacity, pressure and required power to be submitted to the OWNER for approval.

Between pump and gearbox a tooth coupling to be installed. Further a barring arrangement and hand turning means to be provided.

Flushing and gland water to be supplied on suction and shaft side of the sand pump. Each pump to deliver at least 45 m³/h in case of mixture jetting conditions (sand pump pressures above 65 mwc). These flushing and gland water pumps to be driven by the main engine (via heavy V-belts).

1.4.4 Suction pipe

The suction mouth to be dimensioned with an area of about 0.25 m², suitably shaped into the cutter with a height of about 0.25 to 0.30 m and a width of about 0.8 - 1.0 m. Easy mounting/replacement of suction mouth without dismounting the suction line and/or cutter shall be possible.

A rubber suction hose with smooth inner surface and with a length of at least 1100 mm will connect the suction line of the ladder with the suction pipe line on board.

This hose to be suitable for 100% vacuum with a suitable safety factor.

Geometrical position and connections of this hose (including geometrical design of ladder at this location) to be designed for easy replacement.

Additional means as ladders and small platformsetc. for carrying out these replacements to be provided.

The suction pipe line on board to be connected to the dredge pump by means of an expansion pipe with quick-release type connections.

1.4.5 Discharge pipe line

The pressure pipe line on board to be installed with expansion pipe pieces provided shortly after the sand pump discharge opening.

At the aft end of the pontoon a swivel bend (rotation over 180 degrees) with stuffing box to be mounted for connection to the floating pipe line.

The pipe lines to be supported by a suitable number of steel frame structures, taking into account the requirements for jetting .

The discharge line on board to be fitted with a non-return valve.

1.4.6 Jetting nozzle

The mixture capacities etc. and spoil density mentioned are varying in these clauses. For both i.e. discharging through pipeline and nozzle the pump capacity to be such that the mixture capacity is 2600 m³/hr. and spoil density is of 1.30 ton/m³.

For jetting purposes one pipe piece of the discharge line to be replaced by a jetting arrangement consisting of a pipe piece with bend and nozzle pieces. This pipe piece with bend connected by bolts to the discharge line on the forward side (to sand pump) and via a horizontal foundation with blind flange to the ft part of the discharge line. The nozzle to be mounted pointing upwards under several angles between 15 and 45 degrees. Therefore additional bend pieces with flanges to be delivered; 2 x 15 degrees, 2 x 20 degrees and 2 x 25 degrees. Radius of bend pieces about. 1200 mm for centre line of pipe. Throttle to be connected to the bend pieces via a flange connection with a rubber sealing ring, hinge on one side and a low number of breaking bolts on the flange opposite side.

An additional pipe piece of about 3.5.m length to be delivered, mounted on supports and suitable for . connection to bend pieces and nozzle for jetting to other side.

The outlet diameter of the nozzle to be calculated for the required throwing distance, mixture capacity of at least 2600 m³/h and a specific density of 1.3 t/m³.

Nozzle to be constructed of wear-resistant steel with 20 mm plate thickness and to consist of a conical part (diameters 450 mm to about 170 mm) and a straight pipe piece (diameter about 170 mm) each with a length of at least 500 mm. Inside of _nozzle to be designed-for an efficiency of at least 85%.

For the above described structures with foundations and supports the reaction forces of this jetting arrangement to be taken into account. One complete spare nozzle to be delivered.

1.4.7 Floating discharge pipe line

The first sentence in the second para is to be substituted by ‘The pipeline to consist of 450 mm inside diameter high density polyethylene (HDPE) pipes mounted with two floaters’

The pipe line to consist of 450 mm inside diameter High Density poly Ethylene (HDPE) pipe mounted two floaters.

The pipeline to consist of 450mm inside dia of HDPE pipe mounted on 2 floaters.

A floating discharge pipe line with a total length of 500 m to be delivered. In general 12 m (6 m + 6 m) elements are to be interconnected by rubber hoses with a length of 2.0 m and a part of the pipeline will consist of 6 m elements interconnected by rubber hoses.

In total 46 rubber hoses to be delivered and suitable for a working pressure of about 10 bar.

The floating elements to be designed for keeping the dredge line afloat when pumping a mixture with a specific density of 1.6 t/m³ and with a margin of 15% displacement.

All flange connections to be designed with a rubber sealing ring (with canvas inlays), a minimum of bolts and for an axial load due to current of at least 80 kN.

Further for anchoring this pipe line all elements to be provided with suitable connections, and in total 20 anchors I (weight abt. 150 kgs each) with each a wire ,of about. 30 m length to be delivered.

1.5 Hydraulic power unit

The hydraulic supply unit shall be built-up with four identical type and size variable axial piston pumps, normally used for:

- one for side winch drive
- two for cutter drive
- one for general purpose such as pilot, ladder hoisting, spud control etc.

In case of failure of one of the main pumps .(in single pump systems only) there must be a possibility to use one of the pumps for the cutter drive for this duty.

In this case the cutter will be driven by one pump and one motor.

In case of auxiliary diesel failure (for emergency. ladder or for repair-/check-/spud-handling winchoperations electrically driven hydraulic pump set of about 5 kW shall be installed.

All main pump units to be equipped with a power limiting, a pressure limiting and a flow limiting device, based on an open circuit hydraulic loop.

Zero position interlocking to be provided for all controllers during starting-up of the pump set.

Further additional controls to be added as follows:

- a) For the cutter drive and side winches Flow control from the dredging desk (speed control).
- b) For the distribution unit A load sensing device, regulating the pressure between 30 bar (pilot pressure) and max. 160 bar (depending on the maximum required highest pressure during control of one or more simultaneously used consumers).

The normal working pressures (based on the in this specification mentioned lifetime), shall be:

- for the cutter drive (2 pumps and 2 motors) : 100 bar
- for the side winches : 100 bar
- for the distribution system : 30-160 bar.

The hydraulic pump installation is to be built as one complete unit with the tank, filters, cooling unit, valve panels, accumulators, remote control relais, interconnecting piping, instruments and cabling assembled on a common frame which as a unit will be fitted on the ship's foundation.

The tank must have a capacity of approx. 1.5 m³ and provided with all necessary accessories, including low level, high temperature and dirty filter alarm, level indicator, temperature indicator etc.

It must be possible to fill the hydraulic tank from deck. The filling line to be provided with filter. The filling connection to be lockable, e.g. by means of a padlock.

1.5.1 Cutter drive

The cutter drive consists of two hydraulic motors, each connected to a variable displacement pump, parallel operating by pressure equalizing (equal torque).

The speed control from the dredging desk to be stepless by displacement control of both pumps up to about 30 revs/min. of the cutter.

In case of one of the pump units should be used for one of the other systems or is out of use, then the cutter will be driven by one pump-motor combination. In this emergency case the cutter speed range to be the same as for the normal condition.

The max. power per motor to be limited at: -

- for combined 2 motors drive : 75 kw
- for emergency I motor drive (intermittent duty) : 110 kw

The max. system pressure to be limited at 160 bar.

Interlocking to be provided against running without cutter bearing flushing water (flow).

Alternatively 150-170 HP with direct hydraulic drive is consider

Acceptable

1.5.2 Ladder winch drive

The hydraulic motor to be connected to the main hydraulic distribution network and shall be stepless speed controlled from the dredging desk via a pilot controlled two directional proportional valve.

The hoisting and lowering speed to be limited at about 18 m/min. The hoisting force limited at 160 kN. Both on the second layer.

The highest and lowest position of the ladder to be automatically limited by limit switches on the ladder.

For ladder position indicator and pre-warnings of end positions,

1.5.3 Side winches control:

Both side winches, each with one hydraulic motor, will be controlled via one variable displacement pump unit in such a way that only the hauling winch shall be speed-controlled from the dredging desk via the flow control of the pump unit.

The other winch is then disconnected from the pump and is normally veering, with a braking torque adjustable from the dredging desk in five steps between 10% and 40% of the nominal hauling force.

The controls of both winches to be combined in one joy-stick with in horizontal direction the dredging speed control to PS or to SB (including mid-scale zero position) and in vertical direction the braking torque control of the veering winch (without zero position).

The selection "hauling winch-veering winch" will be determined by the (horizontal direction) joy-stick position to PS or to SB, and changes every time when passing the midscale position (stop position).

For separate winch control a 4-position selector-switch to be added in the dredging desk for the following duties:

- individual control PS-winch
- stop (off)
- individual control SB-winch
- combined control (normal dredging).

Joy-stick zero-interlocking to be provided during duty selection.

In the "individual control" condition veering shall be also speed-regulated (as hauling).

Running interlocking to be provided against combined-control with two spuds aground.

Protection of "rolling cutter" to be built in the hauling direction of the SB-winch (e.g. min. hauling torque), which prevents cutter passing the side wire during dredging in case of rolling.

1.5.4 Spud carrier control

The spud carrier cylinder to be controlled, in two (individual, pre-adjustable) speeds for both desk. controlled, in two (individual directions,' from the dredging Limit switches to be provided for disconnection on the end positions.

The maximum pressure limiting devices to be suitable for the full nominal flow.

Spud hoisting control

Both spuds including the clamps to be controlled from the dredging desk.

The hoisting speed (one step) based on about 75% pump capacity.

The spud cylinder to be provided with a built-on pilot pressure relieve valve on plunger side, and two amply dimensioned built-on relieve valves with common return line.

The latter to be as short as possible and to be based on 0.5 m/sec. at rated oil delivery (75% of pump). The spud cylinder on plunger side to be supported by means of a spring or small cylinder with accumulator, for compensation of its weight.

Lowering of the spud should be possible via the cylinder (controlled) or in free fall by means of the clamps.

The necessary time relays should be built-in for interlocking the controls of spud and clamps simultaneously to prevent wrong operation.

The system with two pressure switches or equal system for indication of highest position and unloaded condition

CHAPTER - 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 INTRODUCTION

The aim of this chapter is to provide an overview of the published work that is relevant to the current investigation. Given the scope of the present research, a comprehensive review of all the contributing research is not possible, however the major relevant investigations are explained below.

2.2 PREVIOUS STUDIES OF INTERACTING STRESS CONCENTRATIONS

2.2.1 Overview of Previous Research on Interacting Stress Concentrations

There have been numerous studies of situations involving the interaction of stress concentrations due to the proximity of various geometric features with respect to certain applied loading conditions. Some of these studies are simplistic while others are very complex, involving extensive testing and the use of finite element models to predict stress values at critical locations. The majority of previous research on the phenomenon of Kt interactions is based on a detailed study of a specific situation or situations involving closely spaced features subjected to a particular loading profile. Also, many of the earlier studies on this specific topic are related to aero structures or have been completed with the goal of being used in the aerospace industry. These instances seem to arise or occur in this field more frequently than in any other engineering discipline.

Ling [13] is typically recognized for having conducted the first full-scale research on interacting stress concentrations. In Ling's study, combined Kt effects were analysed for two circular holes in a plate. This situation tends to be the most common example of stress concentration interaction found in aero structures.

Peterson [11] includes a section concerning the effects of multiple stress concentrations. A simplified relationship is presented to attempt to account for the interaction of two stress raising features.

$$K_{t1,2} = K_{t1} \cdot K_{t2} \quad (1)$$

However, Equation (1) is approximate and in most cases considered overly conservative in that the combined stress concentration factor, $K_{t1,2}$, is found to be much larger than the actual value that can be derived through means of testing or applied finite element analysis.

Other relationships have been proposed to account for combined stress concentrations including the root sum squared method identified in Equation (2).

$$K_{t1,2} = \sqrt{K_{t1}^2 + K_{t2}^2} \quad (2)$$

Another simple relationship, presented by Eccles [14], that can be used in the analysis of two interacting stress concentrations is

$$K_{t1,2} = K_{t2} \sqrt{K_{t1}}, \text{ where } K_{t1} \geq K_{t2}. \quad (3)$$

The above Kt interaction Equations (1-3) are limited to only two combined features. Specific relationships must be developed and unique data generated for various cases of geometry and loading related to interacting Kt effects for more than two details.

2.2.2 Two Closely Spaced Holes in an Infinite Plate

One of the most commonly analysed situations involving interacting stress concentration factors is the case of an infinite plate with two closely spaced holes loaded in tension, as shown in Figure 2.1. The direction of loading is perpendicular to the centre-to-centre spacing between the holes.

Figure 2.1. Infinite Plate with Two Circular Holes in Perpendicular Tension

In ESDU Data Item 75007 [15], Geometric Stress Concentration Factors: Two Adjacent Unreinforced Circular Holes in Infinite Flat Plates, it is shown that the K_t values for the small and large holes increase as d/c increases. This translates to a rise in stress concentration factors as the centre-to-centre spacing between holes decreases. This also holds true for two holes of equal size, where $D/d=1.0$. Stress concentration factor values are shown to vary significantly for different D/d ratios.

Separate stress concentration factors are presented for both the small and large holes in [15]. The maximum stresses generally occur at points A and B for the small and large holes, respectively. All K_t values for this situation of geometry and loading approach 3 as c increases, which is the theoretical K_t of a single hole in an infinitely wide plate. This means that as the centre-to-centre spacing between the holes increases, the interacting K_t effects are mitigated. In practice, if $c \geq 4D$ then no combined stress concentration factors need be considered.

For an infinite plate with two circular holes in perpendicular tension, the larger stress concentration factor is associated with the smaller hole. The combined stress distribution depends upon the exact centre to centre distance between the holes and hole diameters. ESDU Data Item 85045 [16], Stress Concentrations: Interaction and Stress Decay for Selected Cases, covers this case in detail. The individual stress distributions for the small and large holes are shown in Figure 2.1.

Peterson [11] also includes stress concentration factor charts for the case of two closely spaced holes loaded in tension with a load direction perpendicular to the centre-to-centre spacing between holes. Similar results and comparable K_t values to those given in ESDU Data Item 75007 [15] were determined. Other studies and research by Graham, Raines, Swift and Gill [17] and Middendorf [18] on this same combination of geometry and loading have confirmed these findings.

The situation shown in Figure 2.1 is considered to be one of the most commonly occurring circumstances of interacting stress concentrations observed in aerospace applications. Closely spaced holes are seen most frequently in aero structures when a hole is misdrilled or mislocated in close proximity to a blueprint hole.

Figure 2.2 Infinite Plate with Two Circular Holes in Parallel Tension

Another similar and common occurrence of interacting stress concentration factors is presented in Figure 2.2. This case of multiple stress concentrations is identical to the one previously shown in Figure 2.1 with the exception that the direction of loading is now parallel to the centre-to-centre spacing between holes.

ESDU Data Item 75007 [15] also covers this combined K_t circumstance. The data presented is somewhat unique in that as d/c increases that is as the proximity of the holes with respect to one another increases, the stress concentration factors for the large hole and small hole tend to decrease. For most K_t interactions, the concern is that stress will go up as the critical features become closer to each other. Here the importance of load direction is illustrated. When the load direction is parallel to the spacing between details, the stress concentration factors decrease as the proximity between features increases.

Once again, the conclusions presented immediately above hold true for a wide range of D/d ratios, including two holes of the same size, where $D/d = 1.0$. The stress concentration factor values are shown to vary according to the ratio of D/d . For the small and large holes, the maximum stresses will generally occur at points C and D, respectively. As d/c goes to zero, or as the proximity of the holes with respect to one another decreases, the K_t values presented for the small and large holes in ESDU Data Item 75007 [15] approach 3 which is the stress concentration factor of a single hole in an infinite plate loaded in tension. It should also be noted that the K_t of the larger hole tends to increase slightly while the K_t of the smaller hole tends to decrease as D/d increases.

Peterson [11] also presents stress concentration factors for the situation shown in Figure 2.2. The results presented by Peterson [11] for two closely spaced holes in an infinite plate in axial tension with a load direction parallel to the centre-to-centre-spacing between holes are taken from ESDU Data Item 75007 [15] and Haddon [19].

In practice, the case of interacting stress concentrations presented in Figure 2.2 is typically ignored. Values of $K_t = 3$ can be conservatively used for both the small and

large holes. However, if a more detailed or accurate assessment of the stresses at the holes is required, analysts and engineers may use the stress concentration factors determined considering the effects of interaction. Again if $c \geq 4D$, then no combined K_t effects should be taken in to account.

Now consider the case of two circular holes in an infinite plate subjected to biaxial loading, as shown in Figure 2.3. This example of stress concentration interaction exists as a combined case of the previous two circumstances of circular holes in an infinite plate, where the loads shown in Figure 2.1 and Figure 2.2 have been superimposed.

Figure 2.3 Infinite Plate with Two Circular Holes in Biaxial Tension

A K_t chart for this combination of geometry and loading is presented in the NASA Astronautic Structures Manual, Volume 1 [20]. It is shown that for various ratios of d/D , the stress concentration factors for the small and large holes increase as $c/2d$ increases. It can therefore be concluded that the case of an infinite plate with two holes in biaxial tension behaves similar to the case of an infinite plate with two holes in perpendicular tension with stress concentration factors rising as the holes become closer to one another. The maximum stresses occur at the points labelled E and F in Figure 2.3 for the large and small holes, respectively. Peterson [11] also presents a

stress concentration factor chart for two closely spaced holes in biaxial tension with data taken from Haddon [19] and Salerno and Mahoney [21]. The graph of K_t values in Peterson [11] for an infinite plate with two holes in biaxial tension is somewhat limited in that only three D/d ratios are considered and P_1 is assumed to be equal to P_2 . Further, it also only provides one K_t to be used for both the small and large holes. The stress concentration values shown in Peterson [11] confirm the findings presented by NASA in [20] for this interacting stress concentration case in that these values increase with a decreasing c/d ratio as the centre-to-centre spacing between holes becomes smaller.

Peterson [11] gives stress concentration factors for different ratios of P_1/P_2 , assuming that the holes in biaxial tension are aligned perpendicular and parallel with the P_1 and P_2 load directions, respectively.

It may sometimes be necessary to consider shear loading with respect to K_t interaction. An infinite plate with two closely spaced holes loaded in shear is presented in Figure 2.4. Situations involving shear loading for closely spaced holes may be seen in aero structures when holes are misdrilled or mislocated in shear webs. These webs typically have a smaller thickness when compared with other parts or details loaded in tension, therefore, the higher stresses caused by interaction of closely spaced geometric features should be accounted for.

Figure 2.4. Infinite Plate with Two Circular Holes in Shear

A graph of stress concentration factors for this case of shear loading is given in ESDU Data Item 75007 [15]. For the various D/d values presented, the separate SCFs for both the small and large holes tend to increase slightly with a decrease in the centre-to-centre spacing between holes. The maximum stresses at the large and small holes occur at points G and H, as shown in Figure 2.4. Whether the maximum stresses are found at the upper G or H points, as opposed to the lower G or H points, is dependent upon the direction of shear loading.

Equations (15) and (16), presented by ESDU in [15], show the relationship between the stress concentration factors for both the small and large holes, $K_{t,d}$ and $K_{t,D}$, the maximum stresses found at the holes, f_d and f_D , and the value of the applied shear stress, q .

$$f_d = K_{t,d} \sqrt{3q^2} \quad (4)$$

$$f_D = K_{t,D} \sqrt{3q^2} \quad (5)$$

Peterson [11] also presents stress concentration factors for interaction between two holes in an infinite plate in shear. Similar results are shown for various D/d ratios in terms of stress concentrations when compared to ESDU Data Item 75007 [15]. For this case involving shear loading, both Peterson [11] and ESDU [15] present results using data taken from Haddon [19].

2.2.3 Closely Spaced Notches

Combined stress concentrations are not limited strictly to circular holes. Kt interaction effects may also be present when notches are placed in close proximity to one another. Figure 2.5 shows two closely spaced notches in a plate of finite width. The critical geometric features are aligned parallel to the primary direction of loading.

Figure 2.5. Two Closely Spaced Notches in a Finite Width Plate

ESDU Data Item 85045 [16] contains graphical data for close proximity notches in a finite width plate. Multiple notches with equal radii are considered. K_t values are presented for two, three, four, and five notches aligned parallel with an applied tension load. The length of the plate is assumed to be infinite. SCF values are plotted versus a ratio of a/r . The K_t chart presented by ESDU in [16] shows that the stress concentration factors decrease from a maximum value at $a/r = 0$ to a minimum value between $a/r = 2$ and $a/r = 8$, depending upon the number of notches placed in close proximity. The stress concentration factors then increase back up to a maximum as a/r increases. This case illustrates the complex nature of stress concentrations involving the effects of both stress decay and stress increases due to interaction. Data presented in ESDU Data Item 85045 [16] is said to be taken from Durelli, Lake, and Phillips [22,23].

The information in ESDU Data Item 85045 [16] for closely spaced notches is somewhat limited in that the requirement of $W/r=18$ must be met for true accuracy. However, it is typically considered acceptable for these stress concentration factor values to be used for analysis in situations where the width of the plate, W , is much greater than the radii of the notches, r . Another requirement is that the notches must be semi-circular in shape.

Peterson [11] also gives K_t values for various combinations of closely spaced notches in finite width plates. All of these charts are for notches positioned in line with the direction of loading. Peterson [11] actually contains identical data to that presented

by Ling [24] for the particular case of close proximity notches. Other data presented in [11] for this combined K_t occurrence is derived from Atsumi [25], Isida [26], Hetenyi [27]. The Peterson [11] charts for closely spaced notches tend to show that the stress concentration factors decrease as the width of the plate, W , increases. These K_t values decrease as the spacing between the notches, a , decreases, exhibiting properties of stress decay.

Closely spaced notches usually exist in aero structures as a design feature. Placing the notches in close proximity to each other with respect to the primary load direction can help to reduce stress concentrations in certain pieces of structure. Multiple notches may also be introduced during repairs of aerospace parts. Discrepancies including damage, gouges, and misdrilled pilot holes may be trimmed out by creating a notch or multiple notches. Fatigue and stress analysts can assist in designing proper repairs for these cases by taking in to account the stress concentration factors that would result from placing notches in locations where none previously existed.

2.2.4 K_t Interaction of Different Geometric Feature Types

Up to this point, this discussion of combined stress concentrations has been limited to interaction between multiple features of the same type. However, some occurrences of interacting stress risers involve two or more types of geometric details. For instance, a hole may intersect a radius, or the stress concentration at a hole may be affected by a nearby notch, etc. Consider the specific case of a hole in a radius as shown in Figure 2.6.

Graham, Raines, Swift and Gill [17] and Graham [28] develop stress concentration factors for the situation of combined SCFs illustrated in Figure 2.7. These factors are dependent upon several variables including the diameter of the hole, the width of the plate, and the distance from the centre of the hole to the root of the radius.

Figure 2.6. Hole in a Radius in Axial Tension

Holes drilled at or near a radius occur frequently in aero structures and are the result of mistakes made by manufacturing in mislocating holes during the drilling operation. Radius blocks are typically used to ensure proper installation of the fastener in the mislocated hole, however adjustments to the stress concentration factor at the hole may be required based on the amount of interference that exists between the hole and radius.

Now consider another case of stress concentration interaction between features with different geometry types, as displayed in Figure 2.7. A hole placed between two fillets is shown, with an axial tension load applied.

Figure 2.7. Hole Between Two Fillets in Axial Tension

Graham [28] presents a stress concentration factor chart for this instance of combined SCFs. This chart identifies a complex relationship between all of the dimensions involved in the problem, including the width of the plate, W , the distance between fillets, b , the radius of the fillets, r , as well as the diameter of the hole and its position with respect to the fillets. Changing any one of these variables can alter the value of the stress concentration factor. The data presented by Graham [28] highlights the added complexity of calculating stress concentration factors for interaction between two or more types of geometric features over those cases involving just one type of geometry.

Stress concentration factor data and charts for other instances of multiple feature types placed in close proximity are presented in Graham, Raines, Swift and Gill [17] and Graham [28]. K_t values for a hole located between opposite notches in a finite width plate are given. It is shown by Graham [28] that for a given ratio of notch radius to plate width, the stress concentration factors tend to rise sharply as the ratio of the hole diameter to the width of the plate increases. This means that as the notches and hole get closer to one another, the K_t values increase.

Considering the relatively high frequency with which multiple geometric detail types are placed in close proximity in aero structures, the amount of previous research that has been conducted with regards to these specific cases of K_t interaction is somewhat limited. Major stress concentration factor references like ESDU [10] and Peterson [11] predominantly present data strictly for K_t interaction involving single

geometric feature types. Analysts and engineers in the aerospace world need K_t charts that provide accurate values for various instances of multiple features placed in proximity.

2.2.5 Other Cases of Stress Concentration Interaction

There exist many other K_t combinations found in aero structures that have not already been discussed in this paper. Previous research has been conducted and unique stress concentration factors have been developed for many of these unique cases. Stress concentration interaction effects are often very complex and can involve consideration of a large number of different geometric features and loading combinations at one time.

Information has been formerly presented in this paper relating to two closely spaced holes in an infinite plate. However, there has been a considerable amount of previous research conducted on two closely spaced holes in finite width plates as well. In aero structure applications, K_t interactions tend to exist in finite width plates just as often as they do in plates categorized as having infinite widths. Figure 2.8 displays a diagram of two closely spaced holes in a finite width plate with a load direction perpendicular to the centre-to-centre spacing between holes.

ESDU Data Item 85045 [16] contains a stress concentration factor graph for this case of combined SCFs. K_t values are given at various d/W ratios. The stress concentration factors are shown to generally decrease as L/W increases. This indicates that the maximum stresses located at the points labelled I in Figure 2.8 decrease as the spacing between the holes increases with respect to the width of the plate. This instance of combined stress concentrations for a finite width plate behaves much like the same combination of geometry and loading in an infinite width plate. The data presented by ESDU in [16] is somewhat limited in that it is only valid for two holes with equal diameters.

Figure 2.8. Two Closely Spaced Holes in a Finite Width Plate

Peterson [11] also shows similar stress concentration factor data for closely spaced holes in a plate of finite width. K_t values are provided considering a load direction parallel to the spacing between holes. For various ratios of d/W , the stress concentrations factors tend to decrease as the d/L ratio increases. Data derived from Schulz [29] was used to obtain these SCF values. Again, these factor derivations are limited to closely spaced holes of equal diameters.

Stress concentration factors for a pinned or riveted joint with multiple holes spaced perpendicular to load direction with respect to one another are given by Peterson [11]. For these pinned joints, the edge distance, or distance between the centre of the holes and the edge of the plate, is taken in to account. It is shown that for various edge margins, which is the ratio of the edge distance over the diameter of the holes, K_t values increase with an increase in the ratio of hole diameter to the spacing between holes. The associated data presented by Peterson [11] is derived from Mori [30]. The stress concentrations are also shown to be higher for lower edge margins. Holes drilled near an edge occur frequently in aero structures and consideration should be given by engineers and analysts alike to the high stress concentration factors that may potentially result from this condition.

Various configurations of patterns of holes in a plate have also traditionally received considerable attention in previous research on K_t interactions. An example of one of these configurations is illustrated in Figure 2.9. This diagram shows a pattern of closely spaced holes in an infinite plate, subjected to tension loading in the axial and transverse directions.

Figure 2.9. Pattern of Closely Spaced Holes in Biaxial Tension

The NASA Astronautic Structures Manual, Volume 1 [20] contains stress concentration factor charts for a number of different combinations of hole arrays subjected to a variety of loading conditions. Peterson [11] is again a good source for SCF values involving patterns of closely spaced holes. These K_t charts provided by Peterson [11] are derived from data presented by Schulz [29], Sampson [31], Meijers [32], Horvay [33], Nishida [34], Bailey and Hicks [35], Hulbert [36], Hulbert and Niedenfuhr [37], Kraus [38] and Kraus, Rotondo and Haddon [39]. These references generally tend to provide data for arrays of holes of equal diameters which is typically how these hole patterns exist in metallic structures.

Stress concentration factor values for arrays of holes placed in close proximity tend to be dependent upon variables such as hole diameter, load direction, centre to centre spacing between holes, and the angle of positioning of the holes with respect to

one another. The holes may be arranged in rectangular, diagonal, square, triangular, or even occasionally, circular type patterns [40]. As is typical of most K_t interactions, stress concentrations tend to rise as the spacing between the features decreases [41],[42].

Patterns of holes are seen in aero structures most frequently in repair doublers that are added to parts by in order to maintain structural stability [43] [44]. These repair plates often contain large numbers of fastener holes that may be placed in close proximity [45], [46]. Arrays of holes can also sometimes exist as a part of the initial design of the structure. In any event, aerospace engineers must have access to accurate stress concentration factors in order to complete a fatigue or stress analysis of critical sections that may contain arrays of holes [47].

Cut outs are another geometric feature that have historically been analysed for stress concentrations. Rectangular cut outs are sometimes placed in close proximity to each other or to nearby holes. Consider the simple instance of stress concentration interaction for two closely spaced cut outs shown in Figure 2.10.

Figure 2.10. Closely Spaced Cut outs in Tension

Sikora [40] presents perhaps the best collection of K_t charts for cut outs of various sizes. Many of the stress concentration factor plots in [40] involve K_t

interaction for two or more cut outs placed in close proximity. This study was published by the U.S. Navy where no doubt the stress concentration effects of cut outs receive considerable attention as these types of details are common to naval structures.

Cut outs are also seen frequently in aero structures. The Comet I disasters discussed in the Federal Aviation Administration Damage Tolerance Assessment Handbook [4] were determined to be caused by high stress concentrations at rectangular window cut outs. This highlights the importance and criticality of developing accurate stress concentration factors for these types of geometric features.

Circular cut outs are used in aerospace applications and are sometimes referred to as "lightening holes". These "lightening holes" are employed as a weight saving measure in certain structural components. These circular holes may be rather large when compared to typical fastener holes. Stress concentration factor charts that cover circular holes may not necessarily contain data that would provide Kt values for large circular cut outs especially in cases of interaction. Therefore, other Kt charts that cover these types of details must be used or developed as required.

The information relating to stress concentration factors presented by Sikora [40] includes various situations involving single rectangular cut outs, closely spaced rectangular cut outs, circular holes and rectangular cut outs placed in close proximity. The SCFs given are naturally dependent on the height and width of the rectangular cut outs, the spacing between cut outs, and the direction of loading.

2.3 Research Objective

The main purpose of this research is to study the effect pretension loss and the effect of stress concentrations due to the assembly level gap on the offshore structural component. Distinct stress concentration modification factors are developed to assist engineers conducting metal fatigue analysis for instances involving hole/radius interference. Finite element analysis methods are used to derive these factors.

CHAPTER 3

METAL FATIGUE

3.1 Definition of Fatigue

A standard definition of the term fatigue, as it applies to metals, from ASTM E1823 is, the process of progressive localized permanent structural change occurring in a material subjected to conditions that produce fluctuating stresses and strains at some point or points and that may culminate in cracks or complete fracture after a sufficient number of fluctuations. A more straightforward definition for fatigue is the nucleation of cracks in a structure resulting from cyclic loading.

Voids or slip planes that are inherent in the material join together to form these cracks. The three chronological stages a fatigue crack undergoes are

1. Crack Initiation
2. Fatigue Crack Growth
3. Ductile Separation

The fatigue strength of a material differs from the static strength in that the static strength is related to a single applied load while the fatigue strength is dependent upon repeated loading that varies over time.

Classical fatigue theory is typically considered valid for metals only. Composite materials exhibit fatigue related properties that cannot necessarily be covered by typical fatigue analysis methods and relationships. The study of the phenomenon of fatigue in composites is ongoing and more research is needed to come to a better understanding of how these complex materials react to repeated loading. Although composites are used

extensively in aero structures, the research contained in this study is limited strictly to metals.

Some commonly used terms and equations related to a typical cyclic fatigue loading profile are presented. Figure 3.1 shows a representative fatigue loading cycle.

Figure 3.1. Cyclic Fatigue Loading Profile

$$\text{Stress Range:} \quad \Delta S = S_{\max} - S_{\min} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Stress Amplitude:} \quad S_{\text{alt}} = \frac{S_{\max} - S_{\min}}{2} \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Mean Stress:} \quad S_{\text{mean}} = \frac{S_{\max} + S_{\min}}{2} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Stress Ratio:} \quad S = \frac{S_{\min}}{S_{\max}} \quad (4)$$

Fatigue analysis and fracture mechanics, the science behind damage tolerance, are sometimes grouped together. However, it should be noted that fatigue and fracture mechanics are actually separate disciplines. The goal of proper fatigue analysis for design is to ensure that a crack will not initiate or nucleate for a desired life. In fracture mechanics, it is assumed that a crack of a certain specified length already exists and the amount of time it takes, or number of cycles needed, to grow the existing crack to a critical length is determined. Each discipline has its own unique methods and set of commonly used relationships. Fatigue is concerned with concepts including S-N curves and stress concentrations while the theory and study of fracture mechanics includes the use of da/dN curves and stress intensity factors.

3.1.1 A Historical Perspective of Fatigue

The first study of fatigue, relating to a structural change in metals due to repeated loading, dates back to 1838 when Wilhelm Albert [2] conducted research on hoisting chains used in mining. Jean-Victor Poncelet, a French engineer and mathematician, coined the term fatigue to describe the wearing down of a material due to changes in loading in 1839 during lectures at a military school in Metz, France. The first in-depth fatigue analysis involving testing and the development of S-N curves is credited to August Wohler [3] in 1860 for a study of failures of railroad axles.

Much of this early fatigue-related research was conducted due to a need to analyze metallic machinery that was used extensively during the Industrial Revolution of the 19th century. A large amount of new information has been generated and many original analysis methods have been developed relating to fatigue subsequent to these early studies. Research on fatigue in aerostructures, important because of the typical loading and unloading conditions that exist, has played a critical role in the development of the science of metal fatigue since the advent of flight in the early 20th century. Many fatigue failures and disasters in aerostructures have been recorded. The in-flight disintegration of a Comet I airplane in 1954 after a long service history is one of the first notable failure events in aerospace that was attributed to fatigue. The

particular airplane that failed was actually the first passenger plane with a jet engine to go in to active service. Just a few weeks after the first Comet I event, another Comet I disintegrated inflight. All service of the aircraft was then immediately suspended. Subsequent testing, as detailed in the Federal Aviation Administration Damage Tolerance Assessment Handbook [4], revealed that the cause of the disasters was a fatigue failure originating at the cabin windows.

The widespread fatigue damage (WFD) failure of Aloha Airlines Flight 243 in 1988 is another catastrophic event attributed to the effects of cyclical loading. In this accident, an entire section of the upper cabin was blown out. The Boeing 737 aircraft was actually well beyond the certified design service goal when the fatigue failure occurred. A passenger is reported to have noticed a crack in the fuselage skin prior to the flight. The plane was forced to make an emergency landing and one person was killed. The National Transportation Safety Board accident report [5] identified corrosion as the primary cause of the fatigue cracking in this incident. A picture of the Aloha airplane just after landing, which illustrates the massive damage caused by metal fatigue, is shown in Figure 1.2.

Figure 3.2 Aloha Airlines Flight 243 - Fatigue Failure Due to Corrosion [6]

There have been many other disasters and events involving fatigue in aerostructures, some of them very recent. The Los Angeles Times [7] reported that in

April of 2011, a Southwest Airlines Boeing 737 was forced to make an emergency landing after a visible tear opened in the upper fuselage skin causing some cabin depressurization. Subsequent inspections found fatigue cracking in the critical region. These incidents indicate the necessity of proper and detailed fatigue analysis in the design and maintenance of aircraft as well as a need for continued research related to the effects of loading and unloading on aero structures.

3.2 Stress-life Approach

There are different methods commonly used to conduct fatigue analysis of metals. Stress-Life, Strain-Life, and some applications of Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics (LEFM) can all be employed when attempting to predict the nucleation of cracks in metals. The Stress-Life or S-N approach is the most frequently used and well established method of fatigue life prediction.

Hence diversity could be defined based on the least attacking effort (the shortest path). There are actually several possible ways for choosing such shortest paths and for defining the metric.

To conclude, the existing researchers have taken a first step towards formally modelling network diversity as a security metric for evaluating networks' robustness against zero day attacks. They first devised an effective richness-based metric based on its counterpart in ecology. They then proposed a least attacking effort-based metric to address causal relationships between resources and a probabilistic metric to reflect the average attacking effort. They provided guidelines for instantiating the proposed metrics and discussed how software diversity may be estimated. Finally, they evaluated the algorithms and metrics through simulations. Their study has shown that an intuitive notion of diversity could easily cause misleading results, and the proposed formal models provided better understanding of the effect of diversity on network security. The main limitations of this work and corresponding future directions are as follows.

The Wohler diagram, more commonly referred to as the S-N curve, provides the basis for the Stress-Life method of fatigue analysis. This plot, which is derived from empirical test data for a specified material, shows a relationship between the alternating stress and cycles to failure. An example of an S-N Curve is displayed in Figure 1.3.

Figure 3.3. Typical S-N Curve

The test data used to generate an S-N curve is good for a specified R value. The endurance limit is an alternating stress for which a certain metal will never experience fatigue failure as long as the stress remains below this value.

Figure 3.4. Unnotched vs. Notched S-N Curves

Figure 3.4 illustrates the effect that notches have on a typical S-N curve. The notched specimen will have a shorter fatigue life at the same stress level compared to the unnotched specimen.

3.2.1 Variable Amplitude Loading

Fatigue loading is generally represented as a spectrum, which is a series of maximum and minimum cycles of loading that are grouped together. These loading cycles have varying stress amplitudes. This is true especially in aero structures that are often subjected to complex load patterns. A diagram of a simplified spectrum is shown in Figure 3.5.

Figure 3.5. Fatigue Spectrum Loading

To analyze a structure for variable amplitude loading, the concept of a damage ratio is introduced. The damage ratio, D_i , at a particular stress level in the spectrum is defined as

$$D_i = \frac{n_i}{N_i} \quad (5)$$

where n_i is the number of cycles at a certain stress and N_i is the number of cycles to failure at that same stress.

Miner [9] has developed an important relationship in metal fatigue analysis that can be used for life prediction. Miner's rule states that fatigue failure will occur when the sum of the damage ratios for all of the stress levels in a given spectrum is greater than or equal to one. Miner's rule is given by Equation (6).

$$\sum D_i = \sum \frac{n_i}{N_i} \geq 1 \quad (6)$$

For variable amplitude loading in aero structures, the ground-air-ground, or GAG, stresses are the maximum and minimum stresses reached in the entire spectrum. The GAG Damage Ratio can be defined as

$$\text{GAG Damage Ratio} = \text{GAG Damage} / \text{Total Damage} \quad (7)$$

If it is assumed that the spectrum represents variable loading for one flight then the predicted fatigue life in number of flights for a critical detail can be found using the concept of GAG stresses and GAG damage by applying Equation (8).

$$\text{Number of Flights} = 1 / (\text{GAG Damage} / \text{GAG Damage Ratio}) \quad (8)$$

This predicted fatigue life can then be used to determine a fatigue margin of safety based on a pre-defined service life objective.

3.3 Stress Concentrations

3.3.1 Definition of a Stress Concentration

ESDU Data Item 64001 [10], Guide to Stress Concentration Data, states that a stress concentration, also sometimes referred to as a stress raiser or stress riser, is defined as a local stress increase in the intensity of a stress field due to discontinuity. Stress concentrations are measured by stress concentration factors, typically denoted by the symbol K_t . In [10], the stress concentration factor, or SCF, is defined as the ratio of the highest stress to a reference stress calculable from simple theory.

Many different sources and references provide K_t charts for various geometries and loading conditions involving features such as notches, radii, fillets, holes, grooves, etc. However, Peterson's Stress Concentration Factors [11,12] acts as the preferred handbook for SCF values. The situation of a hole in a plate loaded in axial tension is displayed in Figure 1.6. The stress distribution in the plate at the hole location is shown. As D/W goes to zero, for an infinitely wide plate, $K_t = 3$.

Figure 3.6. Plate with a Hole Loaded in Axial Tension

A bar with shoulder fillets loaded in tension is shown in Figure 1.7. As r/b decreases or as W/b increases, the stress concentration factor goes up. This means that a small radii, or sharp corner, will have a high K_t .

Figure 3.7. Flat Bar in Tension with Shoulder Fillets

Now consider the case a flat bar with a double notch loaded in tension, as shown in Figure 1.8. As r/b decreases or W/b increases, the value of K_t rises. Smaller radii in the notches or deeper notches will cause the stress concentration factor for this case to increase.

Figure 3.8. Flat Bar in Tension with Double Notch

Stress concentration factors are always dependent upon the specific case of geometry and loading being considered. Engineers must always reference the K_t charts in sources like Peterson [11,12] to ensure that they are using accurate SCF values in their analysis of metallic structures.

3.3.2 Use of Stress Concentrations in Fatigue Analysis

Stress concentration factors play a critical role in any detailed metal fatigue analysis. Within a structure, fatigue cracks are most likely to nucleate in the region where the stress is at its peak. The highest stresses in a body will occur at geometric features including holes, radii, notches, etc. These peak stresses are calculated from stress concentration factors. Therefore it is essential that accurately determined SCFs are used to ensure that a proper fatigue life prediction of any structure has been performed. The use of stress concentration factors in aero structures is particularly important due to the high number of stress raising features that exist in aerospace part design, in particular fastener holes.

For fatigue analysis, the net stress concentration factor, denoted with the symbol K_{tn} , is used. This net stress concentration factor must be calculated to accurately determine the maximum stress at the critical feature. Consider a plate loaded in tension with a hole at the center as shown in Figure 1.9. The critical points at the hole where the peak stress is located are labelled C. The plate has a thickness of h .

Figure 3.9. Plate with a Hole Loaded in Tension

K_{tn} takes in to account the net cross-sectional area in the body at the point of interest. The net stress concentration factor can be written as a function of the gross stress concentration factor, denoted with the symbol K_{tg} , which does not account for the net cross-sectional area in the body at the critical point. For the case presented in Figure 1.9, the difference between K_{tn} and K_{tg} is found in the formula used to the determine the reference stress for each factor.

$$K_m = \frac{\sigma_{max}}{\sigma_{ref,net}} = \frac{\sigma_{max}(W - D)h}{P} \quad (9)$$

$$K_{tg} = \frac{\sigma_{max}}{\sigma_{ref,gross}} = \frac{\sigma_{max}^{Wh}}{P} \quad (10)$$

$$K_m = K_{tg} \frac{W - D}{W} \quad (11)$$

Equations (9-11) are used to calculate gross and net stress concentration factors throughout this research.

3.3.3 Concept of Interacting Stress Concentrations

In certain situations, two or more stress concentrations may interact causing an increase or decrease in the stress concentration factor for each detail. The interaction of

these stress risers is dependent upon the geometric proximity of the features with respect to each other as well as loading conditions. Some of these situations may be relatively simple to analyze and accurate stress concentration factors can be easily developed. Other times, the combined effects are complex and predicting stress concentrations factors for cases of interaction can be challenging.

The word interacting is sometimes substituted with other terms including multiple, superimposed, intersecting, combined or compounding to describe these situations. All of these descriptions have the same meaning and for the purposes of consistency within this research the term interacting is predominantly used.

Interacting stress concentrations can occur in aero structures as a result of a design that specifies two or more geometric features such as holes, radii, notches etc. be placed in close enough proximity to each other that interaction may occur depending upon loading conditions. Circumstances may also arise during fabrication and repair of parts and assemblies that can or will cause stress concentrations of separate details to combine. Mistakes made by manufacturing such as mislocated holes, extra holes, overly sharp radii, holes drilled in radii, extra notches, etc. can be the origin of interacting stress concentrations. Many times these fabrication errors can turn single geometric details with easily determined stress concentration factors in to complex situations of multiple critical features that experience the effects of interaction stress concentrations.

These interacting stress concentrations and their associated stress concentration factors are important to fatigue analysts. The potential rise in stresses caused by the proximity of multiple details considering loading criteria needs to be taken in to account to adequately predict the fatigue life of the structure being studied. The interaction of stress concentrations can cause a significant increase in stresses when compared to situations where only a single stress raiser is being considered. Consequently, interacting stress concentrations can reduce expected fatigue life in aero structures.

Fatigue analysts may use knowledge relating to interacting stress concentrations to suggest and help design details and repairs that will attempt to mitigate the negative effects these interacting features can potentially have on the overall life of a particular structure. Coordination with static stress analysts may also be required. The use of K_t values is not necessarily limited to fatigue analysis. Stress concentration factors can be used to design and study parts and assemblies to ensure that stress allowable are not exceeded.

CHAPTER - 4

SCOPE AND RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

4.1 Scope

This research study focuses on the development of stress concentration factors modification and fatigue damage life for geometric features placed in close proximity with respect to one another. Kt modification factors are commonly applied to account for various conditions that affect the fatigue performance of critical details. Some examples of these conditions include assembly level gap on connection, countersunk holes, inadequate geometry level tolerance, blending, dents, burrs, cold working and flapper peening. The applied mod factors may be either helpful or detrimental to fatigue life.

The assembly level gap developed through this research were determined through finite element modeling and analysis.

The 3D modelling will be done through ANSYS spaceclaim

Meshing and boundary condition will be done through ANSYS Prepost.

Analysis will be carried out through ANSYS Solver.

The research concludes with a general summary of the results. The result values obtained by finite element analysis from the assembly level gap connection are compared with the determined finite element analysis of perfect standard connection result.

4.2 Objectives of the Study

This study consists of an in-depth analysis of various instances that occur in-situ repair, retrofit solution related to the assembly level gap critical connection in offshore structure, onshore structure, lattice tower structural connection, tubular tower flanged connection and heavy fabrication industry during the fabrication or assembly process.

The goal is to provide original result with perfect connection and the result with assembly level gap connection with respect to these specific connections in Heavy Fabrication Industries.

Various thickness shims are introduced in the assembly level gap connection to derive the improved design life.

Comprehensive summaries of the closed gap joint FE Analysis as well assembly level gap FE Analysis are conducted as part of this research project will also be presented in the thesis.

4.3 Research Methodology

4.3.1 Research Purpose

Stress and strain concentrations in assembly level gap in offshore critical structural connections are problematic because it leads to strength deteriorations, damage accumulations and eventually to failure. This paper seeks to establish how the assembly gap get affected by stresses and strains, and the need to shim these assembly gaps.

The influence of the assembly gap and shims on the strains and stresses of a bolted offshore structure has to be carried out using a three-dimensionally nonlinear static analysis using the finite element software ANSYS.

The trend to check the elastic and allowable plastic strain behaviors depicted by the assembled structure with gap and without gap as well the shimming procedure in the offshore structural industry.

The cutter ladder assembly is shown in figure 4.1, it contains

1. A- Frame
2. Cutter ladder
3. Winch
4. Lifting wire
5. Support stay wire
6. Pulleys

Figure 4.1 Cutter ladder Assembly

There are two major load distribution component involved in this analysis.

1. A - Frame
2. Cutter ladder

4.3.2 A – Frame

This is a supporting structure for cutter ladder, the A frame structure are shown in figure 4.2

Figure 4.2 A frame assembly

It is pipe construction with the shape of A , that is the reason it is called A – Frame. Bottom portion of the A frame is hinged with the floating platform and mid of top side is connected with lifting wire, side portion of top is connected with supporting stay wire, the other end of stay wire is connected with the floating platform.

4.3.3 Cutter Ladder

The cutter ladder is structural component and its connections are,

1. One end connected with floating platform
2. Other end connected with cutter
3. In the mid position pulley is connected with A frame main pulley through center winch.

- Side position pulleys are connected with side anchor through side winches.

4.4 Working principle:

The cutter ladder working principles are three condition.

- Horizontal position.
- Water line position
- Cutting position

Considering the above, cutting position is critical and high load is applied on this position only, hence the analysis carried out in the critical cutting position.

Figure 4.3 Horizontal position

In horizontal position the cutter will be above the water level and the cutter load is acting on the A frame.

Figure 4.4 Water line position

In water line position the cutter will be touch on the water level and the cutter load is acting on the center lifting winch.

Figure 4.5 Cutting position

In cutting position the cutter will be cut the underneath surface hence different load action on the cutter ladder unit.

1. Cutter force.
2. All three winch force.
3. Cutter ladder self-weight.
4. Suction pipe slurry weight.

CHAPTER - 5

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

This chapter deals with finite element analysis of A frame and cutter ladder, static analysis is carried out in the A frame to check the strength assessment.

Static and fatigue load is calculated in the cutter ladder unit mainly on the flanged connection, this is critical region for gap formed section due to frequent assembly.

5.1 FEA – “A” Frame

Strength evaluation of the offshore structural ladder gantry (A- frame).

- Deformation limit.
- Stress level.
- Buckling capacity.
- Weld strength.

5.2 Approach

- The procedure was accomplished with the following steps:
- Symmetry model has been considered for analysis.
- The supporting rope and the U-bolt (which connects the rope to A-frame) are not considered for analysis. But the top end point of rope is used to give constraints.

- The pulley where the load is attached is not considered for analysis. But the pulley attaching plate is considered.
- The A-frame is considered as held at 45 deg. If this assumption changes, the FEA results may vary.
- Dynamic load factor has not been considered for the analysis.
- Load arising out of sea wave motion has not been considered for analysis.
- Since the horizontal support pipe has been shifted from middle position to the present position, it could lead to a long column condition.
- Buckling analysis has been performed for this structure to check for critical buckling load. Refer Appendix 1 and 2 for the results of buckling analysis.

5.3 Model characteristics

- Linear elastic material properties considered for all components.
- Quasi-static loading of structure.
- FE models of beam including stiffeners are meshed with linear hexahedral elements.
- Neglect of small holes and edges.
- Model units: N, mm, t, s.

5.4 Coordinate systems

The coordinate system is determined by the CAD models. Orientation of the axes is chosen in a way that y-axis is pointing upward along the tower axis; x- and z-axis are oriented so that a right handed coordinate system is created.

5.5 CAD Model

The offshore structure A frame structural components are detailed shown in figure 5.1 to 5.5 for better visibility.

Figure 5.1 Geometry of A frame, elevation

Figure 5.2 Geometry of A frame, side view.

Figure 5.3 Geometry of A frame, bottom view

Figure 5.4 Geometry of A frame, detailed view.

Figure 5.5 Geometry A frame, hinged joints.

5.6 Symmetrical CAD Model

The CAD model, boundary condition and load conditions are symmetrical about XY plane. So only one half of the model is considered for this analysis.

Figure 5.6 Geometry symmetrical.

5.7 Material Properties

Material properties of all used materials are given in Table 5.1. The A frame assembly is fabricated using EN 10025 – 2, S 355 JR steel.

Mass of the complete structure is 780.350 Kg

Mass of (half model) symmetrical model is 90.175 Kg

Material properties according to (5) are given in Table 5.1.

Table 5.1: Material properties

Part	Material	Young's modulus (MPa)	Poisson's ratio	Yield strength $R_k=R_p0.2$ (MPa)	UTS R_m (MPa)	Density (kg/m ³)
A frame structure	S355 JR	2.1e005	0.3	350	530	7850

5.8 Contact conditions

All welded and bolted connections are modeled with bonded (always) contact. This means, if a node is found to be in contact, the node is constrained in the directions normal and tangential to the contacted body, so no separation, penetration or sliding can occur in case of found contact.

5.9 Boundary condition 1

The A frame structure bottom pin connection faces are considered as hinged joint in the analysis as shown in figure 4-6, because there is no welded and bolted connection in this location.

Figure 5.7 Bottom hinged faces.

5.9.1 Boundary condition 2

Half of the A frame structural faces are applied in symmetrical boundary condition as shown in figure 5.7.

Figure 5.8 Symmetrical boundary conditions applied on the selected faces

5.9.2 Boundary condition 3

Two stay wire is supported to the A frame on its both end points, that wire ropes are constrained in all directions except rotation about its Z axis which is kept free as shown in figure 5.8.

A center node is created at the center of the hinge face by using R-bars. Coupling degrees of freedom is applied between this center point and the rope top point in all directions except the rotation about Z axis.

Figure 5.9 Stay wire supported node

5.10 Gravity load

All calculations include gravity load:

$$F_{\text{Grav}} = gM \cdot m \cdot g$$

With

m ... denotes the mass

g ... the gravitational constant

$gM = 1.35$ safety factor for gravity.

Gravitational constant is applied as acceleration by defining

$$a = gM \cdot g$$

$$a = 1.35 \cdot 9.81 \text{ m/s}^2 = 13243.5 \text{ mm/s}^2.$$

This is necessary to predefined earth acceleration does not allow to change value of g to include the factor of 1.35.

Figure 5.10 Acceleration applied on the COG.

5.11 Lifting load

According to (2) lifting load is applied 8.5 tons with a partial safety factor of 2.

$$F_{cift} = F_{lift} * F$$

$$F_{lift} = 8.5 \text{ ton} * 2 = 17 \text{ ton.}$$

Safety factor F is set to 2 according to (2) which is shown in Figure 5.10).

Figure 5.11 Load applied on the A frame structure.

5.12 Load pattern

All the load cases were summarized in one calculation run. Gravity load is applied in all load cases. As an example a summary of all the load cases are given in Table 5.2.

Table 5.2: Load applied on A frame structure

Load Case No.	Load Case Name	load (N)	Gravity (mm/s ²)
1	Force	170000	13243.5

CHAPTER 6

STRESSES AND DEFORMATION

6.1 Deformation

The criterion for serviceability is recommended in a way that maximum bending deformation of a structural component shall not be larger than the maximum free span divided by 200 for applied load. Maximum allowed deflection is defined by (1) as maximum floor span L of spreader beam divided by 200:

$$R_d = L / 200$$

Where L = approx. 5270mm

$$R_d = 5270 / 200$$

$$R_d = 26 \text{ mm}$$

The deformations are shown in figure 6.1 to 6.4.

The resultant deformation is 0.91 mm which is approx. 1mm. This deformation is well within the allowable limit.

Figure 6.1: Deformation (mm) of A frame in x-direction.

Figure 6.2 : Deformation (mm) of A frame in y-direction.

Figure 6.3 Deformation (mm) of A frame in z-direction.

Figure 6.4: Resultant deformation (mm) of A frame.

The directional deformations are shown in below table 6.1.

Table 6.1: Directional deformation (mm) of A frame

SL No	Description	Direction	Deformation - mm
1	Deformation	X	0.843
		Y	0.648
		Z	0.117
		Resultant	0.914

6.2 Stresses

The resulting stresses of A frame are shown in figure 6.5 to figure 6.18.

The stress is below the allowed limit of 355 MPa in A frame structure.

Figure 6.11 to 6.12 shows the plots of von mises stresses of A frame beam assembly for applied load (linear elastic material behaviour). Deformation scaling is set to 1.0 for all load cases.

Figure 6.5 Stress plot of A frame- X direction, view-1

The maximum stress is occurring in 500 X 500 X 30 size plate because that portion is very near to load applied area, which is well within the allowable limit.

Figure 6.6: Stress plot of A frame- X direction, view-2.

The stress plot is plotted for maximum tensile stress of 35 MPa, Inference The maximum stress is occurring between $\text{Ø} 219$ and $\text{Ø} 273$ pipe welds due to bending, which is well within the allowable limit.

Figure 6.7: Stress plot of A frame- Y direction, view-1

The maximum stress of 49.9 Mpa is occurring in the lofting plate at restraint area, which is well within the allowable limit.

Figure 6.8: Stress plot of A frame- Y direction, view-2

The stress plot is plotted for maximum tensile stress of 35 MPa, the maximum stress is occurring between $\text{Ø} 219$ and $\text{Ø} 273$ pipe weld due to bending, which is well within the allowable limit.

Figure 6.9: Stress plot of A frame- Z direction, view-1

The stress plot is plotted for maximum tensile stress of 44 MPa, the maximum stress is occurring between $\text{Ø} 219$ and $\text{Ø} 273$ pipe weld due to bending, which is well within the allowable limit.

Figure 6.10: Stress plot of A frame- Z direction, view-2

The stress plot is plotted for maximum stress of 43.75MPa, the maximum stress is occurring between $\text{Ø} 219$ and $\text{Ø} 273$ pipe and stay wire plate, which is well within the allowable limit.

Figure 6.11: Von Mises stress plot of A frame- Z direction, view-1

The maximum stress of 89.71 Mpa is occurring in $\text{Ø} 273$ pipe due to bending. The von Mises stress has contribution from compressive stress also, which is well within the allowable limit.

Figure 6.12: Von Mises stress plot of A frame- Z direction, view-2

The stress plot range is plotted between of 0 to 55 MPa, the maximum stress of 51.63 Mpa occurring between $\text{Ø} 219$ and $\text{Ø} 273$ pipe weld due to bending, which is well within the allowable limit.

Figure 6.13: Shear Stress plot of A frame- XY plane, view-1

The maximum shear stress of 24.2 Mpa occurring between $\text{Ø} 219$ and $\text{Ø} 273$ pipe weld due to tensile force, which is well within the allowable limit.

Figure 6.14: Shear Stress plot of A frame- XY plane, view-2

The maximum shear stress of 26.5 occurring between $\text{Ø} 273$ pipe and lifting plate weld due to compressive force, which is well within the allowable limit.

Figure 6.15: Shear Stress plot of A frame- XZ plane, view-1

The maximum shear stress of 13.4 Mpa occurring between $\text{Ø} 219$ and $\text{Ø} 273$ pipe weld due to tensile force, which is well within the allowable limit.

Figure 6.16: Shear Stress plot of A frame- XZ plane, view-2

The maximum shear stress of 21.36 Mpa occurring on $\text{Ø} 273$ pipe outer surface due to compressive force, which is well within the allowable limit.

Figure 6.17: Shear Stress plot of A frame- YZ plane, view-1

The maximum shear stress of 22.5 Mpa occurring between $\text{Ø} 273$ pipe and 9 b plate weld due to tensile force, which is well within the allowable limit.

Figure 6.18: Shear Stress plot of A frame- YZ plane, view-2

The stress plot range is plotted between 22.49 MPa to -21 MPa, the shear stress is occurring between $\text{Ø} 273$ pipe and lifting plate weld due to compressive force, which is well within the allowable limit

6.3 FEA – Cutter Ladder

The strength analysis of offshore vessel drilling structure with component stresses resulting from 17 ton lifting load with a partial safety factor of 2, this is considered as per loading parameter. The loads are calculated with FE software ANSYS according to the loading application.

6.4 Approach

The procedure was accomplished with the following steps:

- Generation of FE model of offshore drilling structure in ANSYS Workbench.

- Introduction of loads and boundary conditions.
- Loads are equally distributed to the structure from cutter unit.
- Structural one end is considered as fixed support.
- Cutter cutting force is considered as cutting load.
- Lifting winch load is considered in upward direction.
- Side winches force is considered in horizontal direction.
- Suction pipe mass is considered along with slurry of 1.3t/m³ density.
- All welded connection is considered as bonded contact.
- Static stress calculations and deflection are carried out using ANSYS.

6.5 Model characteristics

- Linear elastic material properties considered for all components.
- Quasi-static loading of structure.
- FE models of beam including stiffeners are meshed with linear hexahedral elements.
- Neglect of small holes and edges.
- Model units: N, mm, t, s.

6.6 Coordinate systems

The coordinate system is determined by the CAD models. Orientation of the axes is chosen in a way that y-axis is pointing upward along the tower axis; x- and z-axis are oriented so that a right handed coordinate system is created.

6.7 Geometry

The drilling unit with suction pipe structural arrangement is shown in figure 6-19.

Figure 6.19: Geometry of cutter unit, elevation

6.8 Mesh

The mesh is created by the means of ANSYS Workbench's Hex Dominant method. Mesh properties of all components used for the calculation in this report are summarized in Table 6. These meshes are described in more detail in the following sections.

Table 6.2 : Summary of element and node numbers of the models

Component name.	Nodes	Elements	Element type
Cutter unit assembly	118357	277846	Solid185

Table 6.2 present the mesh for all components of the cutter ladder assemblies used to calculate stresses at all components. Mesh size is chosen between 3mm to 80mm in general for the cutter unit assembly and its components.

Figure 6.20 Mesh on cutter ladder

Figure 6.21 Mesh on cutter ladder – detailed view.

6.9 Material Properties

Material properties of all used materials are given in Table 3-3. The cutter unit assembly is fabricated using IS 2062 grade B steel. Material properties according to (5) are given in Table 3-2.

Table 6.3: Material properties

Part	Material	Young's modulus (MPa)	Poisson's ratio	Yield strength $R_k=R_p0.2$ (MPa)	UTS R_m (MPa)	Density (kg/m^3)
Cutter Unit	IS 2062 Gr B	2.1e005	0.3	235	360	7850

6.10 Contact conditions

All welded and bolted connections are modeled with bonded (always) contact. This means, if a node is found to be in contact, the node is constrained in the directions normal and tangential to the contacted body, so no separation, penetration or sliding can occur in case of found contact.

6.11 Boundary conditions

6.11.1 Fixed support

The cutter unit centre of gravity is located 1.5 meter away from the pipe edge, it is connected through the pipe surface through rigid connection via remote point which is shown in Figure 6.22.

Figure 6.22 Remote point for cutter CoG.

The cutter ladder unit centre of gravity is connected its remote location through rigid equation, this is required to capture the exact weight of the cutter ladder assembly, which is shown in figure 6.23.

Figure 6.23 Remote point for cutter ladder structure CoG.

The suction pipe centre of gravity is connected its remote location through rigid equation, this is required to capture the exact weight of the suction pipe along with slurry, which is shown in figure 6.24.

Figure 6.24 Remote point for suction pipe CoG.

The combination of remote point location for the centre of gravity of following components are shown in figure 6.25.

1. The Cutter unit remote location.
2. The cutter ladders structural remote location.
3. The suction pipe remote location.

Figure 6.25: combined remote point in cutter ladder structure.

6.11.2 Gravity load

All calculations include gravity load:

$$F_{\text{Grav}} = g_M \cdot m \cdot g$$

With

m ... denotes the mass

g ... the gravitational constant

$g_M = 1.35$ safety factor for gravity.

Gravitational constant is applied as acceleration by defining

$$a = g_M \cdot g$$

$$a = 1.35 \cdot 9.81 \text{ m/s}^2 = 13243.5 \text{ mm/s}^2.$$

This is necessary to predefined earth acceleration does not allow to change value of g to include the factor of 1.35. The acceleration is shown in figure 6.26.

Figure 6.26: Acceleration applied in cutter ladder structure

6.11.3 Fixed Support

The cutter ladder pipe face is arrested all degree of freedom by providing fixed support, which is shown in figure 6.27.

Figure 6.27 Fixed support on pipe face

6.11.4 Lifting load

According to (2) lifting load is applied 8.5 tons with a partial safety factor of 2.

$$F_{\text{cift}} = F_{\text{lift}} * \square_F$$

$$F_{\text{lift}} = 7.5 \text{ ton} * 2 = 15 \text{ ton.}$$

Safety factor \square_F is set to 2 according to (2).

- 100kN mass is applied on the Cutter unit remote location, which is shown in Figure 6.28.
- 5kN mass is applied on the suction pipe remote location, which is shown in Figure 6-29.
- 150kN mass is applied on the cutter ladders structural remote location, which is shown in Figure 6.30.

Figure 6.28 Remote Load applied on the cutter unit.

Figure 6.29 Remote Load applied on the suction pipe.

Figure 6.30: Remote Load applied on the cutter ladder structure.

6.11.5 Load pattern

Calculations are performed with Ansys workbench in a way all the load cases were summarized in one calculation run. Gravity load is applied in all load cases. As an example a summary of all the load cases are given in Table 3-3.

- Ladder winch lifting load is applied 130kN as shown in figure 6.31.
- Left side winch load is applied 130kN as shown in figure 6.32.
- Right side winch load is applied 130kN as shown in figure 6.33.
- All load combinations are shown in figure 6.34.

Figure 6.31: Ladder winch lifting load applied on the cutter ladder structure

Figure 6.32: Left side winch load applied on the cutter ladder structure

Figure 6.33: Right side winch load applied on the cutter ladder structure.

Figure 6.34: Bolt pretension applied on the flanged joints.

Figure 6.35: All load combination applied on the cutter ladder structure.

Table 6.4: Load combination applied on Cutter ladder structure

Load Case No.	Load Case Name	load (N)	Gravity (mm/s ²)
1	Cutter load	100000	13243.5
2	Cutter ladder mass	150000	13243.5
3	Suction pipe mass	25000	13243.5
4	Center winch	130000	13243.5
5	Left side winch	130000	13243.5
6	Right side winch	130000	13243.5
7.	Bolt Pretension	187000	13243.5

6.11.6 Plausibility check

To establish plausibility of results, deformation plots are checked to ensure cutter ladder drilling unit deformation direction is consistent with applied loading. As an example, directional deformation in y-direction for applied load is shown below which is consistent with applied loading. Hence plausibility of FE model is established.

Figure 6.36: Direction deformation (mm) of cutter ladder structure in y-direction.

6.11.7 Deformation

The criterion for serviceability is recommended in a way that maximum bending deformation of a structural component shall not be larger than the maximum free span divided by 200 for applied load. Maximum allowed deflection is defined by (1) as maximum floor span L of spreader beam divided by 200:

$$R_d = L / 200$$

Where L = approx. 7000mm

$$R_d = 7000 / 200$$

$$R_d = 35 \text{ mm}$$

The actual deformation is 13.3 mm, this is well within the allowable limit of 35 mm.

Figure 6.37: Total deformation (mm) of cutter ladder assembly.

6.11.8 Stresses

The resulting stresses of cutter ladder unit are shown in figure 4-3 to figure 4-4.

The stress is below the allowed limit of 235 MPa in cutter ladder structure.

Figure 6.39 to 6.40 shows the plots of von mises stresses of cutter ladder structure assembly for applied load (linear elastic material behaviour). Deformation scaling is set to 1.0 for all load cases.

Figure 6.38: Von mises stress plot of cutter ladder structural assembly.

Figure 6.39: Von mises stress plot of cutter ladder flange and reducer.

6.12 Fatigue Analysis:

The fatigue data is considered based on the Recommendations for Fatigue Design of Welded Joints and Components – IIW collection as per figure 6.40.

Figure 6.40 S-N Data

6.12.1 Software:

Andy's n coder software is used to perform fatigue analysis, where the static analysis results are converted to fatigue SN curve data sheet.

FAT 36 data are used to evaluate this fatigue analysis for this loaded component like bolt, weld, flanged and reducer part.

Material:

The SN data taken from figure 6.40 ,below figure 6.41 shows the SN data for FAT 36 in Ansys material library.

Figure 6.41 FAT 36 data

6.12.2 RESULT:

The fatigue result for this total component is shown in figure 6.42, it show few component has failure with fatigue damage life. To find out the damage life individual component results are find out in the below steps.

Figure 6.42 Fatigue damage result

From the above result it seems reducer part and bolt region got damage failure. It is proven that the gap is induced more stress on the bolt hence the bolt got fatigue failure.

CHAPTER - 7

RESULT AND CONCLUSION

7.1 Result on a frame:

7.1.1 Stresses

The maximum stress occurring in the structure is well within the yield stress of the material. The results are summarized in the below table 7.1.

Table 7.1: Stress plot of A frame

SL No	Description	Direction	Maximum Stress - Mpa
1	Normal Stress	X	40.153
		Y	34.16
		Z	44.17
		von Mises	89.714
2	Shear Stress	XY Plane	26.451
		XZ Plane	21.36
		YZ Plane	22.493

7.1.2 Deformations:

The deformations are found 0.914 mm, which is well within the allowable limit, which are shown in table 7.2.

Table 7.2: Deformation plot of A frame

SL No	Description	Direction	Deformation - mm
1	Deformation	X	0.843
		Y	0.648
		Z	0.117
		Resultant	0.914

7.2 Static Result on cutter ladder:

7.2.1 Deformations:

Deformations are found 13.2 mm, which is within the allowable limit of 35mm.

7.2.2 Stresses:

Stresses in the offshore drilling structure are found well below the maximum allowed limit of 235 MPa.

7.3 Fatigue Analysis:

As per the figure 7.1 the fatigue damage failure happened on the bolts due to the flange gap, it is qualified on static analysis but failed on fatigue analysis.

Figure 7.1 Fatigue damage result

This fatigue damage failure is due to the inherence gap on the mating surfaces. Additional external stress reacted on the bolt due to the gap hence the bolt failed due to loss of pretension. This has proven that the assembly level gap in the matting surface will influence its fatigue life.

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JOURNAL PAPERS

1. Ragesh Sathiyam M, and Shreeprakash B, “Finite Element Analysis of offshore Drilling Structure”, IJIRT, Volume 10, Issue 3, August 2023, ISSN: 2349-6002.
2. Ragesh Sathiyam M and Shreeprakash B “strength Assessment of offshore A frame structure by FEA”, JICR, Volume XV, Issue V, May 2023, ISSN: 0022-1945

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Finite Element Analysis of Offshore Drilling Structure

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Abstract- The offshore module drilling rig has developed into an essential component of equipment for offshore oil and gas extraction, particularly for its large potential use in deep water, analysis of its load-carrying capacity assessment is of great significance. The strength analysis of an offshore drilling structural assembly with a lifting load of 15 tonnes and a partial safety factor of 2 is explored in this work. Finite Element (FE) software ANSYS is used to calculate the loads based on the loading application. ANSYS used to define the materials, geometrical dimensions, loads, and boundary conditions for the drilling structures. As a result, deformations are obtained at 13.2 mm, which is less than the permitted maximum of 35 mm. The highest allowable limit of 235 MPa is determined to have stresses that are substantially below the offshore drilling structure. Therefore, the offshore drilling structure fulfils the strength criteria.

Keywords: Offshore drilling structure, FEA, ANSYS, cutting unit, winch, floating platform, pontoon, suction pipe, slurry, boundary conditions and loads

1. INTRODUCTION

Energy resources are a key factor in a nation's continual development and advancement, and the development of many nations depends on the management of such energy sources. The most extensively used energy sources are oil and gas, and the development and use of these resources are crucial measures of the state of an economy. Consequently, there are rigorous standards for both the operation's safety and the equipment's dependability. As the supply of onshore and inshore petroleum resources declines, the petroleum industry has come to agree that deep water oil and gas resources should be exploited. However, the harsh ocean environment makes Deepwater drilling less safe. As a result, severe specifications for offshore drilling equipment are required. As opposed to onshore drilling, offshore drilling uses a drilling riser system to transport drilling rigs and drilling mud to the wellhead. The length of the

riser system is dependent on the depth of the sea. While a flexible joint and telescopic joint on its topside connect it to a drilling platform or a drilling vessel. The riser will deflect and vibrate as it swings with the ocean environmental loads during offshore drilling. Once the drilling riser breaks or falls into the ocean, there will be significant environmental damage and significant financial loss. Under these conditions, it is crucial to accurately predict and manage the dynamics of the drilling riser in order to guarantee the safety of the Deepwater drilling operation. Currently, the theory of strength, stiffness, dependability, and stability as well as the limited test data on derricks are used to construct the methodology for derrick assessment. The evaluation of Derrick made above using linear extrapolation of the scant test data is not exhaustive or scientific. To assess the stress and stresses occurring on its structure, simulation techniques are applied. Studies on the use of drilling risers are widely available today. The marine riser exposed to a combination of random waves and constant current is investigated using the spectrum method to determine the parameters that affected its dynamic response. Then, the static/dynamic assessments of an offshore drilling riser under various environmental circumstances are performed using the ANSYS software. In order to analyse a drilling riser with its two ends hinged in the floating platform, the dynamic analysis model is used. Some researchers prefer to incorporate the dynamic positioning system onto the drilling platform to facilitate platform accessibility while avoiding the excessive riser end angle. In this work, the strength analysis of an offshore drilling structure with a lifting load of 15 tonnes and a partial safety factor of 2 is explored. Finite Element (FE) software ANSYS is used to calculate the loads based on the loading application. ANSYS used to define the materials, geometrical dimensions, loads, and boundary conditions for the drilling structures.

2. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Development of a FE model in ANSYS Workbench for an offshore drilling structure, which analyse the boundary conditions and loads. The cutting unit evenly distributes loads to the structure. One end of the structural is regarded as a fixed support. Cutting load is referred as the cutter's cutting force. Winch load lifting is considered as occurring upward. The force applied by side winches is measured horizontally. Along with 1.3t/m³-density slurry, the mass of the suction pipe is taken into consideration. Every welded connection is regarded as a bonded contact. ANSYS is used to do deflection and static stress calculations.

A. Modelling Of Finite Element

The finite element analysis is explained briefly in below,

a) Model characteristics

- Linear elastic material properties considered for all components.
- Quasi-static loading of structure.
- FE models of offshore drilling structure assembly are meshed with linear hexahedral elements.
- Neglect of small holes and edges.
- Model units: N, mm, t, s.

b) Coordinate system

The CAD models determine the coordinate system. The axes are arranged so that the y-axis goes upward along the tower axis and that the x- and z-axes produce a right-handed coordinate system. Figure 1 specifies the geometry of the drilling unit with the suction pipe.

Table 1. Material properties

Part	Material	Young's modulus (MPa)	Poisson's ratio	Yield strength $R_k=R_p0.2$ (MPa)	UTS R_m (MPa)	Density (kg/m ³)
Cutter Unit	IS 2062 Gr B	2.1e005	0.3	235	360	7850

C. Contact and Boundary Conditions

Bonded contact is used to simulate every welded and bolted connection. This means that if a node is discovered to be in contact, it is confined in all directions normal and tangential to the contacted body. As a result, no separation, penetration, or sliding may take place in the event of discovered contact.

a) Fixed support

Fig. 1. Geometry of cutter unit, elevation

c) Mesh Modelling

The Hex Dominant method in ANSYS Workbench is adopted to generate the mesh. The mesh element is sized from 3 to 50 mm in order to get fine mesh. The offshore drilling structure assemblies' whole mesh, utilised to determine stresses at every component, is represented in Figure 2. For the cutter unit assembly and its parts, mesh sizes are typically used between 3mm and 80mm.

Fig. 2. Meshing of cutter unit – detailed view.

B) Material Properties

Material properties of all used materials are given in Table 1. The cutter unit assembly is fabricated by utilizing IS 2062 grade B steel.

The cutter unit's centre of gravity is 1.5 metres from the edge of the pipe, and it is attached to the pipe surface by a rigid connection at a remote position, as specified in Figure 3 (a). In order to determine the precise weight of the cutter ladder assembly, which is seen in figure 3 (b), the centre of gravity of the cutter ladder unit must be related to its remote location by a rigid equation.

Fig. 3. (a) Remote point for cutter CoG (b) Ladder structure CoG (c) Suction pipe CoG

To accurately capture the weight of the suction pipe and slurry, as shown in figure 3 (c), the centre of gravity of the pipe must be coupled to its remote location through a rigid equation.

The combination of remote point location for the centre of gravity of following components are illustrated in figure 4.

1. The Cutter unit remote location.
2. The cutter ladders structural remote location.
3. The suction pipe remote location.

Fig. 4. Combined remote point in cutter ladder structure

b) Gravity load

All calculations include gravity load:

$$F_{Grav} = g_M \cdot m \cdot g$$

Where, m denotes the mass and g specifies the gravitational constant

$$g_M = 1.35 \text{ safety factor for gravity.}$$

Gravitational constant is applied as acceleration by defining

$$a = g_M \cdot g$$

$$a = 1.35 \cdot 9.81 \text{ m/s}^2 = 13243.5 \text{ mm/s}^2.$$

Table 2. Load combination applied on cutter ladder structure

Load Case No.	Load Case Name	load (N)	Gravity (mm/s ²)
1	Cutter load	100000	13243.5
2	Cutter ladder mass	150000	13243.5
3	Suction pipe mass	25000	13243.5

This is important because changing the value of g to include the factor of 1.35 would violate the preset earth acceleration. Figure 5 displays the acceleration.

Fig. 5. Acceleration applied in cutter ladder structure.

c) Fixed support

Figure 6 illustrates how the cutter ladder pipe face is restrained from all degrees of freedom by a fixed support.

Fig. 6. Fixed support on pipe face.

d) Lifting load

The lifting load is applied 7.5 tons with a partial safety factor of 2.

$$F_{cift} = F_{lift} \cdot \gamma_F$$

$$F_{lift} = 7.5 \text{ ton} \cdot 2 = 15 \text{ ton.}$$

Safety factor γ_F is set to 2 according to (2).

The 100kN mass is applied on the Cutter unit remote location, which is shown in Figure 6 (a). 5kN mass is applied on the suction pipe remote location, which is shown in Figure 6 (b). 150kN mass is applied on the cutter ladders structural remote location, which is shown in Figure 6 (c).

4	Center winch	130000	13243.5
5	Left side winch	130000	13243.5
6	Right side winch	130000	13243.5

Fig. 6. Remote load applied on the (a) Cutter unit (b) suction pipe and (c) Cutter ladder structure

e) Load pattern

Calculations are performed with ANSYS workbench in a same way all the load cases were summarized in one calculation run. Gravity load is applied in all load cases as specifies in Table 3.

Ladder winch lifting load is applied 130kN as illustrated in figure 7 (a). Left side winch load is applied 130kN as shown in figure 7 (b). Right side winch load is applied 130kN as shown in figure 7 (c). All load combinations are shown in figure 7 (d).

Fig. 7. Load applied on the cutter ladder structure (a) Ladder winch lifting (b) Left side winch (c) Right side winch and (d) All load combination.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The strength analysis of an offshore drilling structure with a lifting load of 15 tonnes and a partial safety factor of 2 is explored. Finite Element (FE) software ANSYS is used to calculate the loads based on the loading application.

Deformation plots are examined to confirm that the direction of cutter ladder drilling unit deformation is compatible with applied loading in order to demonstrate the plausibility of results. As an illustration, the following image illustrates directional deformation in the y-direction for applied load, which is consistent with applied loading. Thus, the FE model's plausibility is established.

Fig. 8 (a) Direction deformation (mm) of cutter ladder structure in y-direction and (b) Total deformation (mm) of cutter ladder assembly

The resulting stresses of cutter ladder unit are shown in figure 9. The stress is below the allowed limit of 235 MPa in cutter ladder structure, which shows the plots of von mises stresses of cutter ladder structure

assembly for applied load (linear elastic material behaviour). Deformation scaling is set to 1.0 for all load cases.

Fig. 9. Von mises stress plot of cutter (a) ladder structural assembly and (b) ladder flange and reducer

5. CONCLUSION

In this work, the strength analysis of a drilling structure used offshore with a lifting load of 15 tonnes and a partial safety factor of 2 is investigated. The loads are calculated using the Finite Element (FE) programme ANSYS based on the loading application. As a result, deformations at 13.2 mm, which is less than the allowed maximum of 35 mm, are obtained. It has been established that the offshore drilling structure is significantly more stressed than the maximum permissible limit of 235 MPa. Consequently, the offshore drilling structure satisfies the strength requirements.

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Strength Assessment of Offshore “A” Frame Structure By Finite Element Analysis (FEA)

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Abstract

The structural design specifications of a permanent offshore platform susceptible to wave-induced forces and moments in a steel jacket are significant for designing offshore constructions. Jackets were one of the first constructions utilised in the offshore trade. One of the crucial components of this structure is the “A” framed structure, which is analysed in this work. A structure may fail due to an unstable or poor design. Therefore, the steel jacket frame is designed in Finite Element analysis (FEA). The behaviour of a steel jacket frame can be analysed using a variety of techniques. But, out of all the conventional approaches the FEA is the most useful approach for determining the strength and behaviour of framed structures. FEA involves performing strength and stability analyses, optimising structural designs under design stresses including gravity, wind, waves and deformation. According to the loading circumstances, the offshore “A” frame structure satisfies the strength requirement.

Keywords: Offshore, Jackets, “A” framed structure, Finite Element Analysis (FEA), Stresses and deformation.

I. Introduction

An offshore platform is a sizable building equipped with tools for drilling wells, pulling oil and gas from the ocean floor, processing it, and storing it until it can be transported to land for marketing and refinement. An idealised column structure subject to both vertical and horizontal loads might be used to describe certain offshore structures, such as the jacket, jack-up, concrete gravity platform, and tower. The history of unintended incidents in the oil and gas sector demonstrates that prior offshore disasters have typically resulted in very severe costs in terms of lives lost, economic damage, and environmental contamination. Typical steel frame structure utilised in the offshore industry, which plays a vital role in operating safety and reliable design. These frameworks' primary purposes are to support mechanical apparatus, instrument cables, and pipes for petroleum. One of the factors in choosing the frame is that it serves as a pipe rack since a ruptured pipeline carrying hydrocarbon liquid or gas may increase the damage in a blast accident by escalating the fire from the explosion. A very difficult and creative task is the analysis, design, and building of offshore structures compatible with the harsh offshore environmental conditions. However, the dynamic response evaluation is especially important for waves of moderate heights as it make the greatest contribution to fatigue damage and have significant roles on reliable design and operational safety.

In offshore steel jacket platforms, fatigue is one of the main causes of failure. These platforms undergo routine inspections throughout their lifetimes to evaluate fatigue damage. Crack measurements are a major component of information from fatigue damage inspections. Two procedures can often be done to guarantee manufacturing precision during the assembling process. The first phase is to precisely forecast the type and quantity of welding distortion using theoretical analysis or numerical modelling, and the second step is to implement workable strategies to minimise welding deformation as much as possible. The stresses and displacements in a steel jacket under combined structural and operational loadings are calculated using a finite element model to create a more precise and efficient design. For investigating the dynamic response of offshore structures, the finite element method offers a useful and less expensive approach.

In this work, the “A” frame structure is employed in offshore for the strength assessment. The symmetrical model is adopted for the analysis of structure. The loads are calculated with the aid of FEA software according to the requirement of loading condition.

II. Proposed Methodology

A. Finite Element Modelling

For the post-local buckling behaviour of steel components exposed to axial compression, a finite element analysis model has been developed. To describe the body of the steel section, the finite element model uses a shell finite element and a material characteristics model based on experimental data. To provide consistent displacement conditions at the loading edges, a particular loading or environmental variable is applied. For axial and lateral displacement behaviour, buckling load, ultimate loads, and axial stress distribution, compression between the test result and the finite element result is carried out.

a) Model characteristics

- Quasi-static loading of structure.
- Linear elastic material properties considered for all components.
- Neglect of small holes and edges.
- FE models of A Frame structural assembly are meshed with linear hexahedral elements.
- Model units: N, mm, t, s.

b) Coordinate systems

The coordinate system is determined by the CAD models. Orientation of the axes is chosen in a way that y-axis is pointing upward along the tower axis x- and z-axis are oriented so that a right handed coordinate system is created.

B. Cad Model

The Computer Aided Design (CAD) systems have been developed and are widely utilised in the design, production, and delivery processes in the offshore sectors. These systems make it feasible to instantly check and alter design findings. The offshore structure

“A” frame structural components are illustrated for superior visibility, which is illustrated in figure 1 (a) view of elevation (b) side view and (c) bottom view.

Figure 1: Geometry of A frame (a) elevation (b) Side view (c) Bottom view

Figure 2: Geometry of A frame (a) Detailed view (b) Hinged view and (c) symmetrical

a) Symmetrical CAD model

In the XY plane, the CAD model, boundary conditions, and load conditions are all symmetrical. For this analysis, only one half of the model is consider.

C. Material Properties

Material properties of all used materials are given in Table 1. The A frame assembly is fabricated using EN 10025 – 2, S 355 JR steel.

Mass of the complete structure = 780.350 Kg

Mass of (half model) symmetrical model = 90.175 Kg

Table 1: Material properties

Part	Material	Young's modulus (MPa)	Poisson's ratio	Yield strength $R_k=R_p0.2$ (MPa)	UTS R_m (MPa)	Density (kg/m^3)
A frame structure	S355 JR	2.1e005	0.3	350	530	7850

D. Boundary Conditions 1.2 and 3

The A frame structure bottom pin connection faces are considered as hinged joint in the analysis as shown in below figure 3 (a), because there is no welded and bolted connection in this location.

Figure 3: View of (a) bottom hinged faces (b) S Symmetrical boundary conditions applied on the selected faces (c) stay wire supported node

Half of the A frame structural faces are applied in symmetrical boundary condition as shown in illustrated in figure 3(b). As illustrated in figure 3 (c), two stay wore are held by the A frame at both of its end points, and the wire ropes are restrained in all directions except rotation about its Z axis, which is left free.

E. Gravity Load

All calculations include gravity load:

$$F_{\text{Grav}} = g_M \cdot m \cdot g$$

Where, m denotes the mass, g be the gravitational constant

$$g_M = 1.35 \text{ safety factor for gravity.}$$

Gravitational constant is applied as acceleration by defining

$$a = g_M \cdot g$$

$$a = 1.35 \cdot 9.81 \text{ m/s}^2 = 13243.5 \text{ mm/s}^2.$$

This is necessary to predefined earth acceleration does not allow to change value of g to include the factor of 1.35.

Figure 4 (a): Acceleration applied on the COG and (b) Load applied on the load frame structure

a) Lifting load

The lifting load is applied 8.5 tons with a partial safety factor of 2.

$$F_{cift} = F_{lift} * \gamma_F$$

$$F_{lift} = 8.5 \text{ ton} * 2 = 17 \text{ ton.}$$

Safety factor γ_F is set to 2 according to DIN EN 1993-1-8, which is shown in Figure 4 (c).

b) Load pattern

One computation run is used to summarise all the load instances. In all load scenarios, the law of gravity is applied. Table 2 represents an overview of all the load situations as an illustration.

Table 2: Load applied on “A” frame structure

Load Case No.	Load Case Name	load (N)	Gravity (mm/s ²)
1	Force	170000	13243.5

III. Results and Discussion

“A” frame offshore structure is proposed for improving the strength development and the FAE analysis is adopted to determine the deformation, stresses and shear stress, which is illustrated elaborately in below.

Figure 5: Deformation of A frame (a) X direction (b) Y direction and (c) Z direction
Deformations

The deformations are found 0.914 mm which is well within the allowable limit, which are illustrated in table 3.

Table 3: Deformation plot of “A” frame

SL No	Description	Direction	Deformation - mm
1	Deformation	X	0.843
		Y	0.648
		Z	0.117
		Resultant	0.914

Figure 6: Stress plot of (a) X direction (b) Y direction and (c) Z direction

Stresses

The maximum stress occurring in the structure is well within the yield stress of the material. The results are summarized in the below table 4.

Table 4: Stress plot of “A” frame

SL No	Description	Direction	Maximum Stress - Mpa
1	Normal Stress	X	40.153
		Y	34.16
		Z	44.17
		von Mises	89.714
2	Shear Stress	XY Plane	26.451
		XZ Plane	21.36
		YZ Plane	22.493

IV. Conclusion

In this paper, the “A” frame structure is employed in offshore for the strength assessment. FEA is developed to mimic the effects of material nonlinearity, geometrical nonlinearity, and boundary nonlinearity. FEA involves performing strength and stability analyses, optimising structural designs under design stresses including gravity, wind, waves and operational load as well deformation. As a result, the loading circumstances of the offshore “A” frame structure satisfies the strength requirement and enhance the structure’s safety.

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